

Geographically Coherent Clusterings of Tide Gauge Stations based on Time Series with Missing Data

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Johanna Hillebrand

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Univ.-Prof. Dr. Melanie Schmidt

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Abstract

Global sea level rise, driven by global warming, has been a critical issue of discussion in recent decades. Although the ocean covers approximately 70% of the Earth’s surface, our understanding, particularly of historical sea levels, remains incomplete. This thesis investigates the use of connected clustering to derive insights into global sea level behavior from local tide gauge records, which date back to 1807. Unlike satellite altimetry data, available only since 1993, tide gauge records contain several challenges: uneven global distribution with a significantly higher density on the Northern Hemisphere, inconsistent time spans, missing data, and a high volume of records making manual analysis unfeasible. Consequently, clustering presents itself as the suitable method to extract meaningful information about global sea level behavior.

The primary clustering objectives in this context are: ensuring similarity of the time series of tide gauge stations within the each cluster, reducing the number of tide gauge stations through clustering, and lastly maintaining geographical coherence within clusters. Given that the tide gauge stations are located along the coastline in a graph-like structure, connected clustering on a line graph is a particularly suitable approach, giving exact results in polynomial time, as introduced by Drexler et al. [Dre+22]. To meters the dual requirements of geographic coherence and time series similarity, we introduce a novel input graph — the *sea level line graph* — that integrates both factors, enabling efficient clustering. Several pre-processing techniques, such as time series partitioning, mean centering, and detrending, are used to optimize the comparability of tide gauge records.

To study the suitability of connected clustering, we use the cluster centers to approximate the mean global sea level. However, the basic connected clustering does not yield evenly distributed cluster centers globally, leading us to development a new method, called *equitable connected clustering*. This method partitions the globe and calculated connected clusters based on the ocean area in each section. We subsequently refine this approach by combining the Voronoi diagram and the sea level line graph to generate a more sophisticated partitioning strategy.

Finally, we combine the elements of this thesis by implementing a global sea level reconstruction approach that uses the clustered tide gauge data, as well as observations from satellite altimetry in order to produce a complete grid of sea level height data. Our results show that Voronoi based equitable connected clustering outperforms the other approaches investigated in this thesis, and yields better results than using a larger number of tide gauge stations.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

70% of the Earth's surface are covered by the Ocean. It has an important influence on global heat and moisture distribution and thus impacts the weather and by extension water and food supply [Jet24]. Additionally, through its ability to exchange heat, moisture and carbon dioxide with the atmosphere it has been an amazing support system in moderating the immediate effects of greenhouse gas emissions. The concerning global rise of sea levels due to human made climate change in recent history and an increase in dramatic weather events such as storms, heat/cold waves and flooding/droughts (see [Rum12]) urge us as humanity to study the behavior of the ocean more closely.

Since 1992 NASA, NOAA, ESA and other organizations have been working to track global ocean topography through satellite altimetry (see “Why Study the Ocean?” by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, NASA [Jet24]). However, this satellite data does not extend further into the past, making the long-term records collected by tide gauge stations around the world invaluable. The [Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level \(PSMSL\)](#) collects, processes and publishes sea surface height data, sourced from national authorities, with records dating back to 1807 (see [Per24c][Per24d]). However, as shown in [Figure 1.1a](#) the tide gauge stations are not evenly distributed and the ocean areas that each station represents vary significantly ([Figure 1.1b](#)). This brings us to the central focus of this thesis. Simply using all measured values from the tide gauge stations to deduce information about the global sea level behavior and its rise over the last century would introduce a significant bias towards the sea level be-

havior in the Northern Hemisphere, as the density of tide gauge stations there is higher than on the Southern Hemisphere. Therefore, it is advisable to only consider a subset of the data measured by the tide gauge stations. If the goal were to simply reduce the number of tide gauge stations, it would be easy to just select a random evenly distributed set across the map. However, this approach risks selecting stations with a unique behavior that are not suitable indicators of the sea level behavior in their geographic region.

To obtain a more comprehensive understanding of global sea level behavior, we aim to group the tide gauge stations. Specifically, we seek to cluster stations that are both geographically close and measure similar sea level changes over time, replacing them with a representative, their cluster center. This approach allows for a more efficient analysis of global sea level changes due to a reduction of data points, without sacrificing critical information. Clustering based on these two criteria — geographical proximity and similarity of time series — poses a unique challenge, as it requires the integration of two distinct distance measures. As illustrated in [Figure 1.1a](#), tide gauge stations are distributed along the coastline, thus naturally forming a graph-like structure. Therefore, a graph can be used to encode the required geographic information. To address these specific circumstances,

we use a specialized method known as *connected clustering*, introduced by Drexler et al. [Dre+22] that was devised with this application in mind. The core concept of connected clustering is that clusters need to be connected by edges in a predefined input graph in addition to the other clustering requirements in question. Among other contributions, the authors introduce an exact, polynomial-time algorithm for the connected clustering problem on line graphs. While this algorithm is a perfect fit for the problem discussed above, its application presents several challenges. These include generating an input graph that takes the geographical conditions into account and defining

(a) Distribution of tide gauge stations.

(b) Voronoi diagram showing the area that each station covers.

Figure 1.1: Distribution of Tide Gauge Stations on the Globe. (b) presents the Voronoi diagram which shows the area each Tide Gauge Station covers. In (a) each location of a Tide Gauge Station is marked with a green dot.

appropriate criteria for determining the similarity between two time series. This thesis addresses these challenges, along with other considerations, and provides an in depth analysis of the resulting methods for the application of reconstructing global sea level values.

To summarize, in an effort to address a small part of this issue, we want to apply algorithms for the connected clustering problem — a problem where an underlying graph and a connectivity constraint are added to the classical clustering problem — to a practical problem from the field of geodesy, namely to gain information about global sea levels from local tide gauge data. We begin this exploration with a description of the underlying data in [Chapter 2](#), followed by the theoretical foundations of connected clustering in [Chapter 3](#). In [Chapter 4](#) we discuss in what way the data needs to be preprocessed and how the input graph for the connected clustering problem is designed. The next two chapters ([Chapter 5](#), [Chapter 6](#)) explore the practical application of connected clustering by proposing new approaches to enhance its suitability for the approximation of the global mean sea level and the reconstruction of global sea levels via [Principal Component Analysis \(PCA\)](#). These approaches, referred to as *equitable connected clustering* and *Voronoi based equitable connected clustering* are introduced and analyzed. Lastly, the key findings are described in [Chapter 7](#), followed by a discussion of future work.

1.2 Sea Level Measurement Systems

To provide a clearer understanding of the measurements that are a basis of this thesis, we offer a brief overview of how tide gauge stations operate and how satellite altimetry data is generated.

1.2.1 Tide Gauge Stations

Traditional tide gauge stations, as illustrated in [Figure 1.2](#), typically utilize a float installed inside a stilling well (see [\[Uni24\]](#)). More modern stations, while similar in construction, use an acoustic sounding tube for measurements. Both types measure the relative sea level with respect to a geodetic benchmark. The first version uses mechanical floats and is more common in older tide gauge stations whilst the second and more modern version works by sending an audio signal down the sounding tube and calculates sea level based on the return time of the reflected signal [\[Nat24\]](#). The sensors from modern tide gauge stations provide regular measurements (for example every six

minutes) which are merged to provide either the **Mean Sea Level (MSL)** or the **Mean Tide Level (MTL)** as described in **Subsection 2.1.1**. Measuring the sea level is only one component of these monitoring stations, as they also monitor values such as wind speed and direction, air and water temperature and barometric pressure and the stations are not primarily built in service of global sea level measurement, but to enable safe navigation, habitat restoration and preservation and other coastal activities (see [Nat24]).

Due to post-glacial rebound or tectonic uplift, there is the possibility of vertical movement that is not associated with a rise or fall in sea level [Nat24]. This, along with the already mentioned uneven distribution across the globe makes determining changes in global sea level difficult. However, the records from tide gauge stations are the only existing source for historical, precise and long-term sea level data (see [Uni24]). Another important complication when using the measurements from the tide gauge stations, is that the reference datum is somewhat arbitrary. The sea level height is determined relative to a benchmark, but as adding GPS-receivers to tide gauge stations is not common practice, the height of the sea level in reference to the ellipsoid is not known. This creates difficulties when for example comparing the measured sea level with the sea level determined via satellite altimetry.

Figure 1.2: Tide Gauge Measurement System based on [Nat24]

1.2.2 Satellite Altimetry

Satellites used for gathering altimetry data follow an orbit that is precisely calculated. They carry a sensor transmitting either microwave or laser pulses and receive the return signals that have been reflected from the Earth's surface. According to the Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS) [SPH24] the radar observation technique is particularly suitable for measurement over the ocean, due to the reflective properties of water. As the exact location of the satellite in reference to a global ellipsoid is known, the distance between the satellite and the ocean surface can be calculated by multiplying half of the round-trip time multiplied with the speed of light [SPH24]. The height

of the sea surface with respect to the ellipsoid is then determined by subtracting this value from the satellites altitude. As the reality is slightly more complicated than this simplified explanation, several corrections need to be applied to the calculated value. However, this basic understanding of the mechanisms suffices for the purpose of this thesis, more information can be found for example in [SPH24].

1.3 Related Work

Connected Clustering Connected clustering as a subfield of clustering has been extensively studied by Drexler et al. [Dre+22], who propose exact algorithms for cases where the input graph is a line or a tree, and an $O(1)$ -approximation algorithm for the disjoint connected k -center and k -diameter problem for Euclidean spaces of low dimension and for metrics with doubling dimension. The connected k -center problem has additionally been studied by Ge et al. [Ge+08], who investigate its applicability to the area of gene clustering and community detection and propose a greedy approximation algorithm. Related to these studies, Gupta, Pancholi, and Sabharwal [GPS11] investigated the connected k -median and k -means problems and propose an $O(\log(n))$ approximation algorithm for the Star Connected 2-Median problem which is a special case of the connected k -median problem. Liao and Peng [LP12] explored a topic that is related to this thesis insofar that they apply connected clustering to spatial data. They utilized local search on an input graph to find clusters that are geographically close and similar regarding their optimization domain.

Sea Level Data Analysis Clustering methods have additionally been utilized to classify patterns in regional sea level behavior. Several research groups apply clustering techniques to sea level data. For instance, Rashid et al. [Ras+19] use k -means clustering in their approach to develop an indicator for extreme sea level for the contiguous United States coastline (see [Ras+19], [RW20]). Their approach identifies regions where storm surges (a rise of water due to a storm) exhibit coherent behavior, allowing for local grouping of tide gauge stations.

Another significant approach was proposed by Scotto, Alonso, and Barbosa [SAB10], who used agglomerative hierarchical clustering to group regional records based on long-term predictions of extreme wave events. This method groups time series according to the similarity of their predictive distributions of return values, with the analysis focusing on tide gauge data from the North Atlantic

to capture regional variability in sea-level extremes. Additionally, Barbosa et al. [Bar+16] use hierarchical clustering to group time series that are similar regarding their wavelet variance (wavelet decomposition aims to identify the most important scales or resolutions of sea level data) and atmospheric pressure in the Baltic Sea.

While somewhat similar, this thesis focuses on a global scale and extended time periods. Additionally, we do not focus on extreme events, but cluster the tide gauge stations based on overall similarity of their time series. Furthermore, unlike previous approaches, we incorporate connected clustering, which accounts for both geographic proximity and temporal variance. Notably, connected clustering on a line graph can be solved optimally, while other methods rely on approximation algorithms.

In addition to clustering methods to classify the underlying data, there are several approaches to derive information about global sea level behavior from tide gauge data. Douglas [Dou91] used selected long-term tide gauge records to infer global sea level rise, while Church et al. [Chu+04] proposed a method based on Kaplan et al. [Kap+97] that combines long-term tide gauge data with satellite altimetry to reconstruct a global sea level grid for time periods prior to satellite altimetry observations. This thesis examines whether connected clustering could enhance these methods by systematically reducing the number of tide gauge stations while achieving an even distribution.

Chapter 2

Sea Level Data

This chapter is an introduction to the data sets, similarity measures as well as the evaluation criteria that are used in this thesis.

2.1 Data Sets

This thesis utilizes three distinct data sources. The first is the [PSMSL \[Per24d\]](#) data set, collected, published and maintained by [Holgate et al. \[Hol+13\]](#) and contains observed data from tide gauge stations. The second source is data generated by the [Ocean Reanalysis System 5 \(ORAS5\)](#) ocean model, which is provided by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) [\[Cop21\]](#). The final dataset consists of gridded sea level data from 1993 until the present, derived from satellite observation and made available by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), Climate Data Store (CDS) [\[Cop18\]](#).

2.1.1 PSMSL

The main data set we are using is the [PSMSL data set](#). The [PSMSL](#) provides monthly and annual data about around 1585 tide gauge stations all around the world from 1807 until the present (see [Figure 1.1](#)). These entries are submitted by national authorities to the [PSMSL](#), automatically checked regarding certain errors (see [Subsection 2.1.1](#)) and then assembled to form a continuous time series for each tide gauge station as can be seen in [Figure 2.1](#). Each station is provided with its unique ID in

Figure 2.2: Differing tide gauge station count and distribution in 1860 and 2010.

addition to a name, its location (latitude, longitude), a coastline code (no longer used), station code (no longer used), country, frequency code, time span, quality flag, and completeness of data flag. A challenge that arises when working with this data set is that the time series for the tide gauge stations start and end at different points in time. As can be seen in Figure 2.2a and Figure 2.2b, the total amount of stations as well as their distribution were quite different in 1860 compared to 2010. Furthermore, almost all time series have gaps in them, which are indicated by the value -99999 in the data set. Another issue is that the data for some tide gauge stations is provided in the form of **MSL**, whereas for others the **MTL** is given.

Figure 2.1: Time series of tide gauge station 1, located in Brest, France.

Mean Sea Level vs. Mean Tide Level The difference between **MSL** and **MTL** lies in the way it is calculated. To obtain the **MTL**, the average of mean high water (MHW) and mean low water (MLW) over a given period of time is calculated, whereas for the **MSL** regular sample measurements of sea level during a period are taken and the arithmetic mean is calculated (see [Woo17]). According to Woodworth it can be shown that the differences between **MSL** and **MTL** lie within a centimeter of each other in many locations, however in others the difference can be quite substantial (several centimeters). They further state that if **MSL** and **MTL** are combined in a sea level time series in a case where those two differ by more than one centimeter, a false inter annual variability enters the record. As we compare tide gauge stations with each other and are specifically interested in changes

over time, the risk that this occurs is significant. Woodworth suggests to “correct for this difference as far as possible” [Woo17]. The PSMSL generally aims to provide MSL values, however, there are time series which contain both.

Flags The authors of this data set flags for each value in the time series to indicate if there are issues with the respective data and to suggest that it is advisable, to read the corresponding documentation file [Per24b]. They use three different flags, “001” indicating that “the data should be treated with caution”[Per24a] and “010” indicating that there is a MTL value in the MSL time series and “011” that both of these are true.

Revised Local Reference (RLR) data set The PSMSL provide a raw data set containing all values as they receive them from the supplying authorities as well as their Revised Local Reference data set. In the RLR data set, a couple of corrections have been applied, in order to make the time series easier to compare. First, they define the RLR datum at each site to circa 7000 mm below mean sea level, in order to avoid negative numbers in the RLR monthly and annual mean values (for detailed information see [Hol+13]).

Second, in some cases the MTL and MSL are combined in one time series. If this occurred, the PSMSL applied an estimate of the annual average difference (MTL - MSL) to the faulty data and flagged the tide gauge stations concerned. However, they explicitly warn that seasonal differences are not captured by the correction, as they are using the annual average for the station in question. Additionally, they use recent data to correct data between 1800 and the early 1900s, which assumes that the difference between MTL and MSL is not subject to change over time. In cases were the PSMSL believes that the correction does not provide an adequate result (that is uncertainty to greater than 1 cm), they flag these with “011”. In general there are 98 of the 1586 tide gauge stations with a warning associated.

Third, the PSMSL perform a number of checks on the data. They check that the reported monthly mean is consistent with the reported annual mean, check for consistency of the reference datum (as in some cases the reference datum has been changed by national authorities to be consistent with national leveling systems), search for outliers (if these are present, a flag is raised), search for incorrect reference datum information, check if there are “jumps” in the RLR time series, perform tests for data that has been reported as sea level changes below a benchmark, rather than above it, and lastly check for each tide gauge station whether the measurements are consistent with

measurements of stations within a 400 km radius. A full list of the requirements the [PSMSL](#) asks of their contributors can be found in the appendix for more information.

2.1.2 ORAS5

The [ORAS5 data set](#) is built from model data in combination with observations from across the world. They provide continuous, generated data from January 1958 to the present with monthly entries and no gaps. The data is available as a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid, which is around a 28 km x 28 km grid at the equator and a 9 km x 9 km grid in the Arctic. The variables given by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) [[Cop21](#)] cover a wide range such as salinity, sea ice thickness, sea surface temperature, sea surface height and many more. However, we only use the sea surface height. For our purposes it is beneficial to start with a data set that does not have gaps or outliers as a first step in evaluating the algorithms, thus we preprocess the [ORAS5 data set](#) as follows.

Preprocessing For our use case, we do not need grid points but single points that are unevenly distributed across the globe. This is because we want to use this data set as first step in exploring connected clustering of tide gauge stations without the added complications of missing data. Thus, we choose the locations of the tide gauge stations from the [PSMSL](#) dataset to ensure comparability between the two datasets. However, the geographical locations of the tide gauge stations do not necessarily align with the grid points of the ORAS5 dataset. To address this, we map each tide gauge station to its closest grid point, but only if this grid point is located in the ocean and if this grid point is not already taken by another station. The latter point is relevant, because in some geographical regions there is a high density of tide gauge stations (for example in the Mediterranean Sea) and it would distort our clustering results if two tide gauge stations were mapped to the same grid point and thus had the exact same time series.

An additional point to consider is that some tide gauge stations in the [PSMSL](#) dataset are located at the exact (or very close to exact) same location, but have non-overlapping time series. This can occur when a tide gauge station was destroyed and rebuilt or the approach to calculate the sea level value for each month was changed, as combining two parts of a time series that are calculated differently might lead to inconsistencies (see [Subsection 2.1.1](#)). These problems obviously do not occur when selecting a subset of points from the ORAS5 dataset, however they are important to

consider, as simply choosing the closest grid point for every named tide gauge station would lead to duplicates and thus faulty values downstream.

From the 1,036,800 grid points in the ORAS5 we choose 1269 points in this manner and structure this data the same as the PSMSL data with the station ID (of the tide gauge station that was mapped to the grid point) and the latitude and longitude of the selected grid point, keeping the other signifiers of the original PSMSL tide gauge stations but removing all flags, as the ORAS5 data due to its nature as a model does not suffer from erroneous measurements.

2.1.3 Altimetry Data

Lastly, for the evaluation of the clustering results in Chapter 5 and for the reconstruction of global sea levels in Chapter 6, we use the satellite observation data distributed by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), Climate Data Store (CDS) [Cop18]. An exemplary image from September 2020 can be found in Figure 2.3. They provide sea level anomaly data, which describes the water-height above the mean sea surface for a given time and region. This mean is calculated over a reference period between 1993 and 2012. For all time steps they use merged data from two satellites, where one is used as the reference and provides long-term stability as it remains the same one, whereas the other satellite changes and its role is to increase accuracy, sample mesoscale processes and provide coverage for high latitudes (see [Cop18]). The focus of this dataset is set on long-term homogeneity and stability, but if the highest accuracy and best spatial sampling are of importance, the advice of the Copernicus Climate Change Service is to use a different dataset.

Figure 2.3: Sea Level Anomaly for 2020-09-01 [Cop18].

As with the ORAS5 data set, the data is given in a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid but ranges from January 1993 to the present with a five month delay due to processing and validation steps. There are daily and

monthly resolutions available, but we select the monthly resolution for better compatibility with the other data sources. The *sea level anomaly* is provided in meters, so conversion is necessary when combining the information with the *PSMSL data set*.

2.2 Similarity Measures, Global Mean Sea Level and Evaluation Criteria

An important question for this thesis is how to evaluate if a clustering of tide gauge stations is indeed “good” in the sense that it achieves certain goals. This is related to the question of how to compare two or more time series in order to assess their similarity. These questions are addressed in the following sections.

Figure 2.4: Time series captured by groups of tide gauge stations from two different locations. The figures (a) and (b) show the different sea level over time at the selected stations.

2.2.1 Similarity Measures

An important question when comparing two or more time series is how they need to behave to be considered similar. If we look at [Figure 2.4](#), we would probably intuitively say that the different time series in [Figure 2.4a](#) are more similar than the different time series in [Figure 2.4b](#). This seems quite reasonable if we look at the geographic locations of the tide gauge stations that produced the respective measurements, as the ones in [Figure 2.4d](#) are further apart from each other, whereas the tide gauge stations in [Figure 2.4c](#) are quite close to each other on one contiguous coastline. However, we need an objective measure between each pair of time series to calculate the sea level difference between them. For this we use two different measures, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the Mean Absolute Error (MAE).

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) The [Root Mean Squared Error \(RMSE\)](#), also known as the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD), is a measure often used in time series forecasting [[Shc+13](#)]. Given two complete time series $x = x_1, \dots, x_n$ and $y = y_1, \dots, y_n$ the [RMSE](#) is defined as follows:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2}{n}} \quad (2.1)$$

The [RMSE](#) puts an emphasis on more extreme differences, restricting the influence of small ones on the resulting value.

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) When using the [Mean Absolute Error \(MAE\)](#), in contrast to the [RMSE](#), the emphasis is not as much on larger differences, as small and large differences have the same weight. For a pair of complete time series $x = x_1, \dots, x_n$ and $y = y_1, \dots, y_n$ the [MAE](#) is defined as follows:

$$MAE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i|}{n}} \quad (2.2)$$

Both of these measures are only defined for complete time series, yet as already discussed, the [PSMSL data set](#) contains time series with varying start and end dates, as well as gaps. This issue and the solution we propose for it are discussed in the next subsection.

2.2.2 Missing Data

An important aspect to consider when calculating the difference between two time series is how to handle missing values in a given time series. Considering that the [ORAS5 data set](#) (see [Subsection 2.1.2](#)) is based on model data, there are values for every single point in time, but in the [PSMSL data set](#) we frequently have missing values as well as different start and end dates for the tide gauge station measurements. We deem two time series to be incomparable if they do not have any temporal overlap. Thus, we calculate the RMS or MAE for each pair of tide gauge stations that have at least one data point in their time series in common (for each set interval or for the entire time span of its existence, depending on the experiment). As can be seen in [Table 2.1](#), there are a total of 1,237,951 pairs of stations that can be compared to each other, but 26.4% of these do not have temporal overlap and are thus incomparable. For each pair of time series there is an average temporal overlap of 176 data points, which is around 14 years. This overlap is not necessarily contiguous.

Category	Value	Percentage
Total number of pairs of stations to compare	1,237,951	
Incomparable time series	326,030	26.4%
Comparable time series	911,921	73.6%
Average data point overlap for time series	176	-
Total number of data points	706,012	-
Total number of missing values	3,391,781	-
Flagged values	6506	0.9 %

Table 2.1: Comparability of the time series in the PSMSL data set.

The [PSMSL data set](#) contains a total of 706,012 valid data points, with on average 445 valid data points per tide gauge station. If we assume a complete timeline from 1807 until 2023 for every tide gauge station, there are 3,391,781 missing values, but as the number of tide gauge stations increases gradually (see [Figure 4.4](#)), one needs to keep in mind that the missing values are not equally distributed. While it is possible to interpolate missing time intervals in the data, we choose to only consider measured values when calculating the similarity. Hence, for two time series x and y we only calculate the difference for the points in time that both x and y exist. This can have the effect that two time series that only have few values in common are considered to be more similar than two time series that exist in parallel for a longer time. However, interpolating the missing values introduces additional uncertainty into the data set. As a strategy to combat this problem, we

enable the user to provide an overlap threshold, for example enforcing that a center needs to have valid data points for at least 90 % of the time that each of the tide gauge stations in its cluster have valid data points. This is further discussed in [Subsection 4.2.4](#).

2.2.3 Evaluation Criteria

The first set of evaluation criteria considers both the algorithmic and geodetic point of view. These criteria align with the core motivation of this thesis and can be described as follows: First, the sea level behavior at the tide gauge stations that are selected as centers should closely resemble the sea level behavior of the stations within their cluster. Thus, we aim to minimize the difference between a cluster center and its cluster. This is the *k-center objective* (see [Definition 1](#)). Second, we seek a substantial reduction in tide gauge stations that need to be considered for further processing, which translates into minimizing the number of clusters. It is important to emphasize that this should not be at the expense of the minimization of the difference between time series of tide gauge stations. Instead, the goal is to reduce the number of clusters by optimizing the input graph and the comparability of the tide gauge stations. Third, we want geographical coherence. However, this goal can be somewhat neglected in the evaluation, as the underlying line graph structure and the connected clustering algorithm enforce a certain spatial coherence because only tide gauge stations that are connected by edges can be clustered together (see [Definition 2, Section 3.2](#)). In summary, the first set of evaluation criteria are: similarity of the time series of tide gauge stations to their cluster centers, a reduced number of clusters and geographic closeness of tide gauge stations to their cluster center. These evaluation criteria are used in [Chapter 4](#).

2.2.4 Global mean sea level

The second set of criteria considers mainly the geodetic application. The objective is to identify a number of tide gauge stations that effectively approximate the global sea level and that can be used in the reconstruction of historic global sea level. Thus, we can measure how similar the mean time series of the selected cluster centers is to the global mean sea level that can be calculated from altimetry data between 1993 and the present. This metric cannot be applied to clustering solutions prior to 1993 due to the lack of data, however using the time frame during which the comparison is possible can be used as an indicator of the suitability of our method. This validation method is used in [Chapter 5](#). The global mean sea level is calculated by weighting all available values from the

altimetry data set to adjust for the curvature of the earth and taking their mean for every date, thus producing a time series from 1993 until 2023.

For the reconstruction of global sea level from tide gauge data (see [Chapter 6](#)), there are two different validation techniques. First, we can once again compare the reconstructed sea level to the altimetry data in the time interval from 1993 onwards. Second, the reconstruction yields a complete data grid, and the reconstructed time series of a grid point can be compared to the time series of a nearby tide gauge station that was not used in the reconstruction process. More on each of these criteria can be found in the respective chapters.

Chapter 3

Connected Clustering in Theory

This chapter introduces the general field of clustering and the connected clustering approach in particular.

3.1 Clustering

Clustering is a well studied field with a multitude of applications. Its goal can be summarized as follows: “*Cluster analysis techniques are concerned with exploring data sets to assess whether or not they can be summarized meaningfully in terms of a relatively small number of groups or clusters of objects or individuals which resemble each other and which are different in some respects from individuals in other clusters.*” [Eve11]. To summarize, clustering aims to group objects together that are similar and separate those that are not. This might sound like an intuitively easy task, however, it is quite complex in a computational sense, as all of the most well-known clustering problems (*k-center*, *k-means* and *k-median*) are NP-hard.

As we mainly focus on the *connected k-center* problem, the basic *k-center* problem can be summarized by the following example “*Given a set of cities with inter-city distances specified, pick k cities for locating warehouses in, so as to minimize the maximum distance of a city from its closest warehouse*” [Vaz97]. Or described in a more formal way:

Definition 1 (k-center). *Given a set of points P , a number $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and a distance function d on P , the task is to find centers $c_1, \dots, c_k \in P$ such that*

$$\max_{x \in P} \min_{i \in [k]} d(x, c_i)$$

is minimized.

Through a reduction from the dominating set problem, it can be seen that this problem is indeed NP-hard (see for example [Vaz97]).

As with the use case we are studying in this thesis, there are many clustering applications where there is a data set in which some information about the phenomena that are occurring is encoded. In this case, the data set contains information about the general tendencies of rising sea levels in recent history, as well as knowledge about coastal segments where the sea behaves similarly. However, without further processing this knowledge is difficult to obtain. With the unequal distribution of tide gauge stations across the globe, taking them as is might lead to a bias towards phenomena that only exist in certain regions, where the main interest is to obtain a more global understanding of sea level behavior. The number of tide gauge stations and the number of their measurements are too high to manually process their information and to evaluate which ones would act as suitable representatives of others. Thus, this is the perfect application for clustering algorithms, as we want to group stations together where the sea level behavior is similar and select a representative one for each cluster, its cluster center. However, the similarity of a tide gauge stations time series is not the only interesting criterion. When we are looking for a suitable cluster center for a cluster of tide gauge stations, we additionally want to consider geographic coherence of the cluster. One could use bi-criteria clustering for this application, but as this problem is not solvable in polynomial time, this would bring the need for an approximation algorithm. Looking at the structure and distribution of tide gauge stations across the globe (see [Figure 1.1a](#)), it is evident that they are arranged along the coastlines in a graph-like structure. This brings us to the next section, in which we discuss the relatively new idea of connected clustering and the special case of connected clustering on a line graph that can be solved optimally in time $O(n^2 \log n)$ [Dre+22].

3.1.1 Connected Clustering

Connected Clustering is a variation of the classical clustering problem that was introduced by Drexler et al. [Dre+22] and Ge et al. [Ge+08]. For the connected clustering problem, a graph is included in the input, and the constraint that points have to be connected via a path in this graph to their center is added to the respective clustering problem. The problem definition according to Drexler et al. is as follows:

Definition 2 (Connected k -Clustering). [Dre+22] *“In a connected k -clustering problem, we are given points V , a metric d on V , a number k and an unweighted and undirected connectivity graph $G = (V, E)$. A feasible solution is a partitioning of V into k clusters C_1, \dots, C_k which satisfies that for every $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ the subgraph of G induced by C_i is connected.”*

They prove that this problem can be optimally solved in polynomial time if the underlying graph is a line. Thus, as the structure of the tide gauge stations along the coastlines forms a line graph, this exact, simple and fast algorithm is ideal for this application

3.2 Connected Line Graph Clustering

The central algorithm we are applying to our use case is the connected clustering algorithm for line graphs from Drexler et al. [Dre+22]. It was designed with specifically this use case in mind and provides us with an optimal solution for the given input graph and point set. The input for this algorithm is a set of points $v_i \in V$, a line graph on this point set and a radius. With the given radius we determine for each point v_i how far a cluster with its center at v_i can reach to the left and right, such that the distance between v_i and each point in its cluster v_j is lesser or equal to the radius and v_i is connected through edges in the line graph to every v_j . This can be computed in parallel to increase efficiency and needs to be calculated only once. Next, for the first node $v_i = 1$ in the line graph, we search for the point v_j that satisfies the following two demands: First, v_j needs to contain v_i in its (precomputed) cluster and second, the cluster size of v_j needs to be larger than any other cluster that contains v_i . A center is placed at v_j and now we know that the cluster centered at v_j covers all nodes from v_i to another node v_k in its cluster and select the next node v_{k+1} as the start node, determine the largest cluster in which v_{k+1} is contained and continue in this fashion until all nodes are part of a cluster.

If the radius is not known, but a number of k centers is to be determined from the given point set, Drexler et al. propose the use of a technique first used by Hochbaum [Hoc84]. Given the at most n^2 different distances between two points in $V = v_1, \dots, v_n$, the radius of the solution has to be one of them, because it is the distance between a point and its center. These distances can be sorted in time $O(n^2 \log n)$ and then the optimal value for a given k can be found via binary search. Now that the prerequisites have been explained, we can use this knowledge to apply the connected clustering algorithm on a line graph to the data discussed in the previous chapter. This is discussed in the next chapter.

Chapter 4

Connectivity Graph and Data Normalization

In this chapter, we work towards the goals stated in [Subsection 2.2.3](#), namely producing clusterings that adhere to the following three criteria: First, the time series of a cluster center and its associated stations should be as similar as possible (a small clustering radius). Second, the number of clusters that is needed to cluster all stations should be as low as possible (whilst still respecting the first goal) as we want to reduce the number of stations that are needed to represent all other stations. Lastly, the clusters should be geographically coherent, that is the stations that are clustered together should be geographically close to each other.

4.1 Graph Creation

For our calculations of connected clustering solutions, we use an exact algorithm, which means that an optimal solution based on the given input points and the given graph is always found. However, the important caveat here is that the quality of the clustering solution depends on the quality of the input graph, as only stations that are connected by edges can end up in the same cluster (see [Section 3.2](#)).

Figure 4.1: Example of a coastline line graph based on all tide gauge stations.

This means that two tide gauge stations that measure a similar sea level behavior but are not connected, can never end up in the same cluster. Thus, if only stations that are dissimilar are connected in the graph, we will obtain a worse solution than if similar tide gauge stations are connected.

Coastline Line Graph Looking at Figure 1.1a, it is apparent that the tide gauge stations are situated along the coastlines of the landmasses. Thus, it is a straightforward idea to create a line graph that follows along the coastline connecting the stations as they occur; an example of this can be seen in Figure 4.1. Additionally, it seems reasonable to assume that tide gauge stations that are close to each other measure similar sea behavior and thus can potentially be clustered together. To compute a line graph that follows contiguous segments of the coastline, we assign each tide gauge station to its closest landmass, excluding small islands, and more specifically calculate which point on the border of the landmass-polygon is closest to it. The polygons of all landmasses are created using data from the *Natural Earth Physical Vectors* [PVK]. Every station that is the only one assigned to a landmass is temporarily classified as an outlier. In a next step, we iterate over the border of each land polygon that has stations assigned to it and build a line graph step by step by creating an edge between the stations as they occur. Lastly, outliers are connected if they are within a certain distance of each other without creating cycles, as the previous steps likely classify tide gauge stations in archipelagos as outliers. Every station, that is not part of a connected component in the graph, is seen as an outlier and will be assigned its own cluster in the clustering step.

Sea Level Line Graph As a second approach, we propose using additional information in the creation of the graph — the sea level difference over time between each pair of stations. How these are computed is discussed in Section 4.2. The underlying idea is that there might be cases in which taking a small “detour” on the line graph could improve the quality of the line graph (see Figure 4.3), and

Figure 4.2: Example of a sea level line graph based on all tide gauge stations.

as the sea level difference between each pair of stations needs to be calculated for the clustering in any case, we have the option to integrate this information into the line graph during its creation. We calculate the [sea level line graph](#) as follows; first we determine a set of potential neighbors for each

Algorithm 1 Generating a Sea Level Line Graph

```

1: Data: Set of tide gauge stations  $A$ , sea level differences  $S$ 
2: for  $a_i \in A$  do                                     ▷ Group tide gauge stations
3:   for  $a_j \in A$  do
4:     if  $(a_i.lat - a_j.lat) < max\_dist$  and
        $((a_i.lon \times \cos a_i.lat) - (a_j.lon \times \cos a_j.lat)) < max\_dist$  then
5:        $N_{a_i} \leftarrow a_j$                                ▷ Find all potential neighbors  $N_{a_i}$ 
6:     end if
7:   end for
8: end for
9: for  $a_i \in A$  do                                     ▷ Sort groups
10:  sort  $a_j \in N_{a_i}$  by  $S_{a_i, a_j}$ 
11: end for
12:  $g \leftarrow$  empty graph                               ▷ Build graph
13:  $\forall a_i \in A$  add node  $a_i$  to  $g$ 
14: change = True
15: while change do                                     ▷ Iteratively add edges if possible
16:  change = False
17:  for  $a_i \in A$  do
18:    if  $N_{a_i}$  is empty then
19:      continue     ▷ If there are no more possible neighbors, consider the next station
20:    end if
21:    if  $deg a_i < 2$  then
22:      for  $a_j \in N_{a_i}$  do
23:        if  $deg a_j < 2$  then
24:          add edge  $(a_i, a_j)$  to  $g$ 
25:          change = True     ▷ As long as nodes are added, continue while loop
26:           $N_{a_i}.pop(a_j)$ 
27:          break
28:        end if
29:      end for
30:    end if
31:  end for
32: end while

```

Figure 4.3: Example for the case in which the *sea level line graph* allows for a clustering with a smaller radius. Assume that the Coastline Line Graph is created as in Figure 4.3b, then it is not possible to create a clustering with a radius that is smaller than 5 for $k = 2$. Figure 4.3c however can be clustered with a radius of 2 for $k = 2$. The nodes with the same color are in a cluster.

individual tide gauge station $a_i \in A$, where A is the set of all tide gauge stations and because we do not want the stations that are connected by an edge to be geographically distant from each other, we define a neighborhood-polygon that is 10 degrees of latitude and longitude away from a_i at the equator and add all tide gauge stations inside this polygon to the set of potential neighbors N_{a_i} . We multiply the degrees of longitude with the cosine of the latitude of the tide gauge stations location to adjust for the curvature of the earth and thus ensure that each surrounding neighborhood-polygon is of the same size. For each tide gauge station a_i , we sort the neighborhood-stations $a_j \in N_{a_i}$ by their sea level difference to a_i (using the metric of choice, in our case either RMSE or MAE). As these values have been previously computed to be used in the line graph clustering, this step is a simple look up. These first two steps are not dependent on shared information and can be computed in parallel. Then we have the following loop to find the best neighbors for each station: Allow every station a_i to select its “best” neighbor, which is the first entry in the ordered list N_{a_i} . If the first station in the ordered neighborhood list already has a degree of two in the created graph, select the next one in the list. Do this neighbor-finding process again until either every station has exactly two neighbors or the list of possible neighbors for each station is empty. Lastly, for each connected component, check if it is possible to connect it to another connected component that is geographically close in order to reduce the number of connected components.

Hypothesis 1 (Sea Level Line Graph). *Using the sea level line graph leads to an improvement in the solution with regard to the number of clusters for a given radius.*

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Coastline Line Graph										
No. of Clusters	1572	1462	1211	985	787	639	546	458	379	331
Average cluster size	1.01	1.08	1.30	1.60	2.01	2.48	2.90	3.46	4.18	4.78
Sea Level Line Graph										
No. of Clusters	1559	1415	1113	871	674	525	441	368	309	264
Average cluster size	1.01	1.11	1.41	1.80	2.33	2.99	3.56	4.27	5.09	5.96
Differences between no. of clusters	13	47	98	114	113	114	105	90	70	67

Table 4.1: PSMSL — comparison of the number of clusters for the Coastline Line Graph vs. Sea Level Line Graph.

Experiment In order to test [Hypothesis 1](#), we create a Coastline Line Graph and a [sea level line graph](#) based on [Algorithm 1](#) for the [ORAS5](#) and the [PSMSL data set](#) each, calculate clusterings for different radii and evaluate the solution. We use the RMSE to calculate the difference between each pair of time series and as radii, we choose a RMSE of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 mm. Our main focus lies on a smaller radius of around 20 mm for all of the experiments, as we want to cluster tide gauge stations that are as similar as possible, however additional insights can be gained from reporting a broader range of results.

Results As can be seen in [Table 4.1](#) and [Table 4.2](#), using the [sea level line graph](#) leads to consistently better results regarding the number of clusters for each radius. Whilst the number of clusters does not differ as much for very small and very large radii, it is reduced by around 100 clusters for the [PSMSL data set](#), with a consistent improvement of the average cluster size. The comparatively small gain for small radii is due to the fact that there are fewer pairs of stations that have a RMSE that is smaller or equal to the set radius, thus it is not possible to cluster them together, regardless of how the underlying graph looks. For the larger radii, the underlying graph is less important as well, as it is most important that there are connections between a lot of tide gauge stations and the likelihood that they are clustered together is quite high if they do not differ too

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Coastline Line Graph										
No. of clusters	954	657	491	391	334	286	256	230	210	195
Average cluster size	1.33	1.93	2.58	3.24	3.79	4.43	4.95	5.51	6.04	6.50
Sea Level Line Graph										
No. of clusters	917	618	449	353	296	252	218	187	175	164
Average cluster size	1.38	2.05	2.82	3.59	4.28	5.03	5.82	6.78	7.25	7.73
Differences between no. of clusters	37	39	42	38	38	34	38	43	35	31

Table 4.2: ORAS5 — comparison of the number of clusters for the Coastline Line Graph vs. Sea Level Line Graph.

much. As the Coastline Line Graph follows the coast, it is still likely that the tide gauge stations within a graph are similar enough to be clustered together if the radius is sufficiently large.

For the [ORAS5 data set](#) we report improvements of around 40 fewer clusters for radii between 30 and 80 mm. The less drastic improvement when using the [ORAS5 data set](#) might be because the model data has less drastic differences between tide gauge stations that are in the same regions. Still, there is a consistent improvement in the average cluster size of up to 1.27 more stations per cluster. The average cluster size is small for every solution, which is once again due to the uneven distribution of tide gauge stations on the planet. For many of the tide gauge stations on the Southern Hemisphere, there is no possibility of clustering, and thus, these stations will always be their own cluster centers, but it is still interesting to consider the increases in average cluster size that different approaches bring with them.

Another observation that immediately presents itself is the significant difference between the clustering results for the ORAS5 and the [PSMSL data set](#). It is a reasonable assumption that at least part of this difference has its reason in the difference between model data and real world measurements. But we also assume that the shorter time span for the ORAS5 data might play a significant role, as tide gauge stations that are similar between 1880 and 1910 are not necessarily as similar between 1980 and 2010. The next section will be occupied with the investigation of options to improve this, as well as normalization and detrending of the time series.

4.2 Improving Time Series Comparability

In this section we examine the impact of various methods aimed at enhancing the comparability of time series and their subsequent effect in clustering results. Given that the primary objective is to cluster tide gauge stations based on the similarity of their time series, the **RMSE** is used, as it highlights significant differences within the time series. As a first technique to improve the clustered solution, we investigate the influence of partitioning the time series.

4.2.1 Partitioning of the Time Series

We propose calculating clustering solutions for subsets of the entire time span and subsequently combining them into a solution that changes over time. We base this approach on the hypothesis that the similarity or dissimilarity between the sea level behavior observed at a pair of tide gauge station is not necessarily consistent over time. This hypothesis is supported by two primary considerations. First, when utilizing the **PSMSL data set**, clustering the entire time span can result in the selection of tide gauge stations as cluster centers that were not operational for a significant portion of the period. Especially for the distant past, where tide gauge records are sparse, determining a clustering that is computed for all stations that exist at any point in time does not make sense. Second, the representativeness of tide gauge stations relative to those in their vicinity might be subject to change over time. Since tide gauge stations are mostly built close to human infrastructure such as ports, their surrounding environment may be modified by human intervention. Furthermore, the impacts of climate change vary across regions (see [Gre+01]), potentially affecting the suitability of tide gauge stations as cluster centers over time.

Even for the **ORAS5 data set**, the time series span a total of 65 years, and our hypothesis is that calculating one clustering solution for the entire time span might lead to subpar results. As explained above this is even more important for the **PSMSL data set** with its earliest measurements in 1807, as well as the varying start and end dates of and missing values in each time series. The last point poses a unique challenge when using the **PSMSL data set**, as we have to consider the effect that the absence of values for points in time for various stations has on the input graph. This is discussed in greater detail in the next section.

Hypothesis 2. *Dividing the time series for each station into smaller time spans leads to fewer clusters per radius.*

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Clustering entire time span										
No. of clusters	917	618	449	353	296	252	218	187	175	164
Average cluster size	1.38	2.05	2.82	3.59	4.28	5.03	5.82	6.78	7.25	7.73
Clustering time steps										
Avg. No. of clusters	908	607	443	351	293	250	217	193	175	163
Median No. of clusters	907	606	441	351	291	253	216	194	174	164
Min. No. of clusters	888	583	423	343	285	243	210	189	172	157
Max. No. of clusters	929	633	470	359	304	260	228	199	183	169
Average cluster size	1.39	2.08	2.85	3.60	4.31	5.01	5.82	6.55	7.22	7.76
Difference between no. of clusters and avg. no. of clusters	9	11	6	2	3	2	1	-6	0	1

Table 4.3: ORAS5 — Comparison of the number of clusters when using the entire time span vs. clustering for each ten-year interval.

Experiment With the goal to address [Hypothesis 2](#), we use the [ORAS5 data set](#) (the additional steps that need to be taken for the [PSMSL data set](#) are discussed in the next section) and divide the time span (1958-2024) into 10-year intervals. The desired length of the interval can be provided by the user. For each time step, we filter the time series for each tide gauge station such that only the values in the considered interval are present. We then calculate the time series difference ([RMSE](#)) between each pair of tide gauge stations for the given interval and compute a clustering for it. Thus, the center points of the clustering are allowed to change over time. To evaluate the effect this has on the solution, we present the average, median, minimal and maximal cluster size over all time steps for radii 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 mm.

Results As can be seen in [Table 4.3](#), there is an improvement of up to eleven fewer clusters when clustering time steps instead of the entire time span. We suspect that this improvement is not as notable because the number of clusters for the [ORAS5 data set](#) is already quite small and the differences between time series are less pronounced, so there is less room for improvement. Additionally, the time span for which there is data in the [ORAS5 data set](#) is already not as long as for

the **PSMSL data set**. For the **PSMSL data set** we need to take an additional step when partitioning the time series in order to avoid fragmenting the input graph.

4.2.2 Avoiding Graph Fragmentation

As mentioned in the previous subsection, a challenge when using the **PSMSL data set** is that not all stations exist and produce measurements at the same time (see Figure 4.4). If we generate a line graph that includes all tide gauge stations existing at any point in time and subsequently remove the stations that are not present during each specific time span, the resulting graph becomes fragmented, significantly impairing our ability to compute clusters effectively.

Figure 4.4: Number of stations that have data for each point in time.

We test two strategies to solve this issue. For the first one, we calculate a Sea Level Line Graph for all stations and then iteratively replace the nodes (each tide gauge station is represented by a node) that are not present in the current time interval by an edge. Thus, we ensure connectivity, but we do not account for a change in the similarity of neighboring tide gauge stations. This is addressed by the second approach for which we calculate an individual line graph for each time interval considering only the tide gauge stations that are present in this particular interval. We hypothesize that the first approach, whilst being less time intensive, might lead to a greater consistency with respect to the selected centers, as the basic structure of the graph changes less. Contrasting, we assume that the second approach, despite being more time intensive, might lead to better clustering solutions, as a more suitable graph for each interval can be computed. Our hypotheses in this section thus are as follows:

Hypothesis 3 (Time-step clustering). *Splitting the time span into 10-year intervals leads to better clustering solutions with regard to the number of stations per radius.*

Hypothesis 4 (Reducing vs computing new graphs). *Calculating a new Sea level per time step yields better results than replacing nodes that are not present with edges for each time step.*

Hypothesis 5 (Center Stability). *Reducing the Sea Level Line Graph per time interval by replacing missing nodes with edges leads to more stable clustering over time but requires more clusters per radius than calculating a new graph for every time step.*

Experiment To address [Hypothesis 3](#) and [Hypothesis 5](#), we calculate the time series difference (using the [RMSE](#)) and the Sea Level Line Graph for each 10-year time interval from 1807 until 2024 using the [PSMSL data set](#). Additionally, we calculate the [sea level line graph](#) once for all tide gauge stations and then reduce this base graph for every 10-year interval by replacing nodes that do not exist in the time interval by edges. With both scenarios, we calculate clustering solutions for every time span, using the previously calculated time series differences for radii 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100 mm. We then evaluate the clusterings by investigating the average, median and maximal cluster sizes for the time steps and additionally check how often cluster centers reoccur with both approaches. For some applications it might be interesting to have an increased stability of cluster centers which means that cluster centers stay the same for longer periods of time. To investigate our approaches in this regard, we calculate how often centers reoccur over the total time span (but not across radii) and additionally calculate how often each center reoccurs on average.

Results As can be seen in [Table 4.4](#), clustering for time steps provides significantly better results on average than clustering the entire time span, thus, proving [Hypothesis 2](#) to be true. However, the difficulty in comparing the clustering for the entire time span with the clustering for the time steps is that until 1877 there are under 46 tide gauge stations (with only two in the beginning). Thus, the average number of clusters is partly as low, because there are only this few tide gauge stations which need at most 46 clusters to be covered and this influences the average significantly (see [Figure 4.4](#)). This is why our primary focus is on the maximum number of stations involved in time-step clustering, defined as the largest number of clusters occurring within any 10-year interval for a given radius. We report the difference between the number of stations used in clustering the entire time span and the maximum number of cluster centers identified in any time interval for both approaches. However, this does not capture the entire picture either. In addition to the overall decrease in clusters, by using the time-step-clustering-approach we exclude the possibility that a cluster center does not exist for a significant portion of the time that its associated stations exists. This is because both tide gauge stations have to exist in the same time interval to be clustered in the

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Clustering entire time span										
No. of Clusters	1559	1415	1113	871	674	525	441	368	309	264
Average cluster size	1.01	1.11	1.41	1.80	2.33	2.99	3.56	4.27	5.09	5.96
Clustering reduced graph per time step										
Max. No. of clusters	1024	986	875	781	708	612	524	462	406	364
Avg. No. of clusters	363	353	321	285	251	217	189	165	146	132
Median No. of clusters	157	254	147	129	115	102	91	84	75	72
Average cluster size	1.0	1.02	1.08	1.17	1.28	1.42	1.58	1.75	1.95	2.13
Difference between no. of clusters and max. no. of clusters	535	429	238	90	-34	-87	-83	-94	-97	-100
Clustering graph per time step										
Max. No. of clusters	1022	976	849	741	646	556	488	432	377	335
Avg. No. of clusters	362	348	307	266	227	195	171	151	135	122
Median No. of clusters	156	152	142	124	103	89	81	74	67	64
Average cluster size	1.00	1.02	1.11	1.22	1.39	1.56	1.75	1.93	2.15	2.33
Difference between no. of clusters and max. no. of clusters	537	439	264	130	28	-31	-47	-64	-68	-71

Table 4.4: PSMSL — Comparison of the number of clusters when using the entire time span vs. clustering for each ten-year interval when either calculating an individual Sea Level Line Graph for each interval or reducing the precomputed Sea Level Line Graph for each interval. The difference between the number of clusters when computing one clustering for the entire time span and the maximal number of clusters in any of the 10-year time intervals is given for the clustering resulting from the reduced graph as well as for the clustering that is computed when calculating a new Sea Level Line Graph per time step.

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Clustering new line graph										
No. of reoccurrences	7983	7667	6771	5871	4994	4298	3774	3323	2870	2703
Avg. center reoccurrence	5.08	4.91	4.42	4.01	3.61	3.32	3.15	2.99	2.86	2.8
Clustering reduced graph										
No. of reoccurrences	8001	7766	7070	6287	5531	4780	4166	3651	3227	2911
Avg. center reoccurrence	5.1	4.98	4.52	4.27	3.88	3.64	3.38	3.25	3.05	2.97
Difference	18	99	299	416	537	482	392	328	357	208

Table 4.5: PSMSL — Comparison of the number of reoccurrences of cluster centers. The number of reoccurrences shows the total number of reoccurrences, with an average provided below. The average number of stations that exist pro time step is 365.

same cluster for this interval. Thus, it is interesting to consider the average and median number of clusters as well, especially in conjunction with Figure 4.4, as it can be seen that we capture a more accurate representation of the development over time with the time-step-clustering-approach.

Considering the maximal number of clusters, we can see that especially for smaller radii (which are the ones that interest us most, as we want to ensure that we cluster tide gauge station that differ as little as possible), the solution improves significantly with up to 537 fewer clusters. For the larger radii clustering the entire time span yields better results than time step clustering, as the graph for the entire time span is more densely populated and thus it is easier for the clustering algorithm to form large clusters if we allow for a larger difference between the measurements of the tide gauge stations. An important thing to keep in mind is that the input graph that is used when clustering the entire time span is somewhat fictitious, as there is no point in time when all of these tide gauge stations exist simultaneously. Thus, it can be argued that the partitioning of the time series is a more sensible approach, even if the reduction in cluster centers were less pronounced.

Comparing the two different approaches to the construction of the input graph for the time step clustering explained previously in this section, we can see that our hypothesis (see Hypothesis 4) is accurate, as computing the Sea Level Line Graph for each time interval yields consistently better

results than reducing the Sea Level Line Graph for each interval by replacing nodes with edges with up to 62 fewer clusters. To discuss [Hypothesis 5](#), we see that this one is accurate as well (see [Table 4.5](#)), with a higher number of total center reoccurrences for every radius of up to 537 center reoccurrences more. However, when looking at the average center reoccurrence that also take the total number of clusters into account, this difference shrinks, as clustering with the reduced graph produces consistently more clusters, thus inherently having a higher likelihood that cluster centers reoccur.

4.2.3 Mean Centering and Detrending the Time Series

As mentioned in the introduction to this chapter, we need to discuss whether we want to use the relative or the absolute difference between the time series that are derived from a pair of tide gauge stations. In our concrete example the usage of absolute or relative differences is related to the question of how two time series need to behave in order to be considered similar. We can either consider two time series to be similar if the absolute sea level value is similar at each point in time or consider two time series to be similar if the behavior of the sea level at both stations over time is alike. As our goal is to group tide gauge stations together which display a similar sea level behavior, we want to consider relative differences. If we chose absolute sea level differences, a cluster could be prevented to form if the starting sea levels at two tide gauge stations were different, even if they behaved identically from that point in time on forward. Thus, we propose to mean center and linearly detrend each time step of the individual time series before computing the differences, graphs and clusterings. As described by Hofer; “Mean centering is an additive transformation of a continuous variable X . It is performed by subtracting its mean from every observed value of X ” [[Hof17](#)]. Linear detrending, however, describes the process of removing any linear trend from the time series by applying a linear least-squares fit to the data and subtracting it from the data using the SciPy detrend function [[Vir+20](#)]. It is important to note that this removes the trend from the entire time series, which causes the similarity between two time series to be mostly based on the fluctuation and not on the absolute increase in sea level height. Additionally, if too short time intervals are selected, mean centering can reduce the expressiveness of the measured values.

We assume that using mean centered and detrended time series for each time step improves the clustering solution in regards to the number of clusters. This is due to the absolute measured value losing its influence and thus, we expect the differences between tide gauge stations to decrease.

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Clustering										
Max. No. of clusters	1022	976	849	741	646	556	488	432	377	335
Avg. No. of clusters	362	348	307	266	227	195	171	151	135	122
Median No. of clusters	156	152	142	124	103	89	81	74	67	64
Average cluster size	1.00	1.03	1.11	1.22	1.39	1.56	1.75	1.93	2.15	2.33
Clustering mean centered and detrended										
Max. No. of clusters	992	851	671	539	434	362	307	264	229	205
Avg. No. of clusters	355	299	237	186	148	121	101	88	77	70
Median No. of clusters	157	142	118	93	74	59	47	46	41	44
Average cluster size	1.01	1.13	1.34	1.63	1.99	2.35	2.78	3.14	3.55	3.87
Difference between max. no. of clusters	30	125	178	202	212	194	181	168	148	130

Table 4.6: PSMSL — Evaluation of mean centering and detrending the time series. We see a maximal decrease of 212 cluster centers for a radius of 50 mm.

Hypothesis 6. (*Mean centering and detrending*) *Mean centering and detrending each time interval improves the clustering result with regard to the number of clusters per radius.*

Experiment To explore whether using the relative differences between two time series changes the outcome of the clustering, we mean center each time series for each time step (10-year steps) and remove a linear trend from each interval. We do this for both the [ORAS5](#) and the [PSMSL](#) data sets. To investigate whether this preprocessing step is sensible, we compare the results with and without these modifications.

Results The results related to [Hypothesis 6](#) are presented in [Table 4.6](#) for the [PSMSL](#) data set. We observe a substantial reduction in the number of clusters, with up to 212 fewer clusters, depending on the radius. As with the other experiments, the reduction for a radius of 10 mm is rather small as such a small radius offers limited potential for improvement. However, for all other radii, the improvement is significant, with a reduction of over 100 clusters, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach.

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Clustering time steps										
Max. No. of clusters	928	633	470	359	304	260	228	199	183	169
Avg. No. of clusters	908	607	443	351	293	250	217	193	175	163
Median No. of clusters	907	606	441	351	291	253	216	194	174	164
Min. No. of clusters	888	583	423	343	285	243	210	189	172	157
Average cluster size	1.4	2.09	2.86	3.61	4.33	5.06	5.84	6.56	7.24	7.76
Clustering mean centered and detrended										
Max. No. of clusters	776	436	294	225	181	142	125	114	109	102
Avg. No. of clusters	735	412	282	209	166	134	119	109	102	97
Median No. of clusters	740	417	287	211	162	134	120	110	103	96
Min. No. of clusters	696	386	265	195	156	128	111	102	97	92
Average cluster size	1.73	3.08	4.5	6.08	7.65	9.45	10.67	11.59	12.41	13.08
Difference (avg.)	173	195	161	142	127	116	98	84	73	66

Table 4.7: ORAS5 — Evaluation of mean centering and detrending the time series. A maximal decrease in cluster centers is seen for a radius of 20 mm with 195 fewer clusters.

Additionally, the results using the [ORAS5 data set](#) can be seen in [Table 4.7](#). Here it is evident that mean-centering and detrending the time series leads to a significant reduction in the number of center. An important thing to note here is that the difference between the average, median, min and max number of clusters is less pronounced for the ORAS5 data set. This is because the model data has no missing values and all data points are present from 1958 until the present. Thus, the average is more informative than for the [PSMSL data set](#).

4.2.4 Enforcing Time Series Overlap

In [Subsection 2.2.2](#) we explain that two tide gauge stations are deemed comparable, if they have a temporal overlap for at least one point in time. However, this does not guarantee that a center is present during the entire time that the stations in its cluster are present. We enable the user to select a threshold x , which enforces that a station A can only be a center for another station B if it is present for x percent of time during the time that B exists. Thus, we enforce a temporal overlap between a center and the stations in its cluster. This can of course increase the amount of clusters

needed for a given radius, as selecting some centers might be out of the question if they only exist for a short amount of time. So, we likely have to accept a trade-off between the number of centers and the enforced overlap.

Hypothesis 7. (*Enforcing time series overlap*) *Enforcing an overlap between a cluster center and the stations in its cluster leads to an increase in the cluster centers needed.*

Experiment In this experiment we examine the impact of enforcing an overlap between center points and the stations in their clusters on the overall number of clusters. We set the threshold to 90%, meaning that a cluster center needs to have valid data for at least 90% of the time that any tide gauge station in its cluster has valid data. If for example two tide gauge stations are similar regarding their RMSE, but the first one has valid data between 1992 and 1994 and the second one has valid data between 1993 and 1995, neither of them can be a cluster center for the other as their temporal overlap is too small.

Results As we can see in Table 4.8 we need more clusters if we enforce a temporal overlap between a center and the tide gauge stations in its cluster, which was to be expected. Especially when comparing the maximal number of clusters that is needed for any time step, we can deduce that there is an interval in time around the year 2000 (see Figure 4.5), for which comparatively many clusters are needed to cover all stations. Where the maximum number of clusters drops to less than 205 with a radius of 100 mm for the clustering without overlap, enforcing a 90% overlap means that this number is more than twice as high, with 488 clusters.

The maximal number of cluster that are needed for a given radius drops continuously as the radius gets larger for the variant without the constraint. However, for the clustering with overlap, we can see that this is not the case, as the first significant reduction happens at 100 mm. Focussing on the average number of clusters per radius, the results look somewhat different. Here we can see a much more even decline in the number of clusters, even if it is mostly higher than for the traditional

Figure 4.5: Number of centers per clustering radius, displayed for every 10-year interval. For comparison, the red line displays the overall number of stations for each interval (red line).

Radii in mm	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Clustering mean centered and detrended										
Avg. No. of clusters	355	299	237	186	148	121	101	88	77	70
Median No. of clusters	157	142	118	93	74	59	47	46	41	440
Min. No. of clusters	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Max. No. of clusters	992	851	671	539	434	362	307	264	229	205
Average cluster size	1.01	1.13	1.34	1.63	1.99	2.35	2.78	3.14	3.55	3.87
Clustering enforcing 90% overlap										
Avg. No. of clusters	234	225	221	214	208	201	196	194	183	122
Median No. of clusters	60	58	58	56	56	56	56	55	54	53
Min. No. of clusters	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Max. No. of clusters	937	917	911	885	867	856	838	835	779	488
Average cluster size	1.7	1.77	1.79	1.87	1.91	2.03	2.13	2.15	2.23	2.71
Difference between avg. no. of clusters	121	-74	-16	-28	-60	-80	-95	-106	-106	-52

Table 4.8: PSMSL — Enforcing a 90% overlap between the centers time series and the time series of stations in its cluster.

clustering approach. What we can take from this, is that there is an interval in time for which this constraint poses a significant challenge, as the overlap between the time series of the stations seems to be rather difficult constraint to combine with a good, small clustering. But, this does not seem to be true for all time intervals as the average and median number of clusters behave different than the maximum number of clusters. Investigating a different time interval length as well as different overlap thresholds might lead to better results in this regard. Additionally, it would be interesting to check, whether this increase regarding the number of clusters comes with an improvement for other goals. We briefly investigate the latter point in the Appendix, but further research regarding this approach is necessary in the future. This brings us to the next chapter in which we discuss the influence of the clustering method on the similarity of the mean time series to the global sea level over time and approaches to improve the distribution of the cluster centers across the globe.

Chapter 5

Equalizing Cluster Center Distribution

As discussed in [Section 2.2](#), a key objective of this thesis is to derive information about the global mean sea level based on the time series of clustered tide gauge stations. Assessing the validity of this approximated global mean sea level is not an easy task, given the lack of ground truth for most of the time period under consideration, as satellite altimetry data is only available after 1992. Nevertheless, comparing the clustering results with the global mean sea level derived from the [altimetry data set](#) can provide valuable insight into the reliability and suitability of our clustering method.

Method In order to evaluate the suitability of the calculated clusterings, we take the clustered solution as described in the last chapter for different radii between zero and ten centimeters and calculate the mean clustered time series between 1993 and 2023. When choosing a radius of zero centimeters, every tide gauge station is its own cluster, allowing a comparison between choosing all tide gauge stations and the clustered solutions. We mean center the mean clustered time series, because the reference datum for each tide gauge station is arbitrary (see [Subsection 1.2.1](#)), which provides us with the mean relative changes in sea level across the cluster centers. As a ground truth we use the [altimetry data set](#) which consists of a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ degree grid with monthly [sea level anomaly](#) data at every ocean grid point. For each point in time we first weight the grid data by multiplying each value with the cosine of its latitude to factor in the curvature of the Earth. Otherwise, there would be a larger emphasis on data that is closer to the poles as the horizontal width of the grid cells shrinks from 28 km at the equator to eventually zero km at the poles. Then we calculate the global mean sea level by taking the mean of all valid grid point values and convert the result from meters to millimeters to match the [PSMSL data set](#).

This produces a continuous time series with one value per month. For the comparison we can then calculate the difference between the global mean sea level time series and the mean clustered tide gauge data time series by using the **RMSE**. To further evaluate the clustering results we also compare them to a random selection of tide gauge stations of the same size and to a random selection of tide gauge stations of the same size that chooses an equal distribution of tide gauge stations across both hemispheres.

Results As can be seen in [Figure 5.1a](#), clustering the tide gauge stations is advantageous compared to simply using data from all tide gauge stations that are available for a given point in time, as the **RMSE** drops from 30.2 mm to 21.6 mm. The best solution is achieved for a cluster radius of 65 mm with on average 300 clusters. Using a random selection of tide gauge stations of the same size yields consistently worse results than both using all tide gauge stations or any clustered solution (see [Figure 5.1b](#)). However if the distribution of randomly selected tide gauge stations is equalized in regard to the hemisphere, this yields a much better result, as can be seen in [Figure 5.1c](#). This effect occurs because the clustering algorithm is implemented without an awareness of the overall and regional density of tide gauge stations. If the time series of a pair of tide gauge stations is similar enough and they are connected with edges, then they are clustered together, without consideration of an even geographical distribution of cluster centers across the globe. This leads us to the next

Figure 5.1: Comparison of the RMSE between the global mean sea level derived from satellite altimetry data and (a) the clustered solution, and all stations, (b) the random selection of the same size as the clustered solution, and (c) the equally among both hemispheres distributed random selection of the same size.

section in which we consider approaches to integrate the overall distribution of cluster centers into the clustering algorithm.

5.1 Equitable Connected Clustering

In order to include the density of the cluster centers into the connected clustering algorithm, we have to consider how many tide gauge stations are selected in a given partition of the ocean. One important point to keep in mind is that a truly even distribution of selected cluster centers is not possible as the distribution of tide gauge stations across the globe is quite unequal; this can be seen in Figure 1.1a.

The first issue is that the tide gauge stations are only built along the coastline. The second one can be seen when considering for example the African coastline, where there are comparatively few tide gauge stations and as we can not retroactively add data points the goal has to be to equalize the distribution of cluster centers as much as possible whilst working with the constraints of the underlying data set. We propose the following hypothesis:

Figure 5.2: Sectioning of the globe for equalizing the distribution of cluster centers

Hypothesis 8. *Equalizing the density and distribution of cluster centers leads to a better approximation of global mean sea levels.*

Method As an initial test of this concept’s validity, we propose a method called *equitable connected clustering* to achieve a nearly even distribution of cluster centers based on the total area. For this approach we divide the globe into seven sections (see Figure 5.2) and subsequently each of these sections is clustered separately. This number and the sizes of the sections serve as a first

test of the hypothesis; a more refined approach is discussed in [Section 5.2](#). The following steps are taken to cluster these sections, assuming that the desired number of clusters k and the set of tide gauge stations with their associated time series are given. Based on the results of the previous chapter, we calculate an individual cluster solution for every ten-year interval, starting with the year 1992, as the goal is to compare the clustered solution to the [altimetry data set](#). Thus, for each of these intervals the tide gauge stations are filtered such that only those with valid data for the current time step remain. Having first calculated the complete surface area of the Ocean in square meters, we then determine the desired cluster center density per square meter $w_k = \frac{k}{\text{ocean area}}$. The ocean area, as well as all other area calculations, are determined by calculating the area of a geodesic polygon using the PROJ coordinate software library [[PROJ24](#)]. With the center density w_k and the area of each section s_a , the center density for each cluster is $s_k = w_k \times s_a$.

A problem that arises at this point is that not every section necessarily has an amount of tide gauge stations in it that is enough to select the wanted number of cluster centers, especially for larger k . It is still desirable to provide solutions for larger k and thus the remaining open cluster centers need to be distributed among the sections that contain more tide gauge stations. One needs to keep in mind, that this introduces an imbalance into the clustered solution and is a trade-off between the two goals of wanting an equal distribution and wanting more cluster centers. If a strictly equal distribution is the most important goal, one would have to accept an overall smaller number of cluster centers. For the purpose of this experiment, we want to test this method for different k and thus proceed as follows to ensure a proportional distribution of the remaining unassigned cluster centers.

Assuming that for multiple sections s , there are centers that can not be assigned $r = \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} r_s = t_s - s_k$, where t_s are the tide gauge stations in the corresponding section. For each section in which $t_s - s_k \leq 0$ set $s_k = t_s$ such that every tide gauge station in this section is selected as a cluster center because there are too few present. After assigning the desired number of cluster centers to each section in this way we proceed as follows: If $r \neq 0$, set $k = r$ and calculate the desired center density for this new k and proceed with the assignment process as described above. The sections that have already reached their capacity can be ignored in the next iteration. The algorithm proceeds in this manner until k is fully assigned. This method ensures that even if an equitable distribution based on the ocean area of each section is not feasible, the division of remaining cluster centers is still as even as possible. Now that the percentage of k for every section is known, the algorithm proceeds with the connected k -clustering for each section individually by calculating the sea level differences between all tide gauge stations, constructing the [sea level line graph](#), and calculating the cluster centers. In a last step, the partial solutions are straightforwardly merged, as there is no overlap between the different sections. One last important caveat to note is that the algorithm can not find a solution for

every possible k , as connectivity in the underlying graph structure is required and if for example two tide gauge stations are not connected by an edge, a solution for $k = 1$ is impossible, but we have implemented it in such a way that the closest solution is calculated. For this application there is no necessity to have the exact amount of cluster centers that was specified. For a shorter description of this method, see [Algorithm 2](#).

Algorithm 2 Equitable Connected Clustering

```

1: Data: Set of tide gauge stations  $T$ , sections  $S$ , wanted number of clusters  $k$ , a set of time
   intervals, ocean area (in  $m^2$ )
2: wanted center density  $w_k = k / \text{ocean area}$   $\triangleright$  yields wanted number of centers per  $m^2$ 
3: for each time interval do
4:   Filter  $T$   $\triangleright$  exclude stations without valid data for time interval
5:   change = True
6:   while change do
7:     for  $s \in S$  do  $\triangleright$  assign wanted number of centers  $s_k$  to each section until  $\sum s_k = k$ 
8:       calculate section area  $s_a$  (in  $m^2$ )
9:       calculate the number of stations in the current section area  $s_t$ 
10:       $s_k = s_a \times w_k$   $\triangleright$  wanted number of centers for section
11:      if  $s_k > s_t$  then  $\triangleright$  if there are fewer stations than wanted centers
12:         $r+ = s_k - s_t$ 
13:         $s_k = s_t$ 
14:      end if
15:    end for
16:    if  $r == 0$  then
17:      change = False
18:    end if
19:     $w_k = r / \text{ocean area}$   $\triangleright$  as long as not all of  $k$  is assigned, continue
20:  end while
21:  for  $s \in S$  do
22:     $p_s \leftarrow \text{connectedClustering}(s_k, s_t)$   $\triangleright$  calculate partial solutions
23:  end for
24:  combine partial solutions
25: end for

```

Experiments To test [Hypothesis 8](#), we calculate the cluster centers for $k = 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650$ and 700 using [equitable connected clustering](#) as described in [Algorithm 2](#) and calculate the **RMSE** between the mean time series of the clustering results and the global mean sea level derived from the [altimetry data set](#). These are then compared to the **RMSE** mean time series of sets of tide gauge stations of the same size that are chosen randomly, but with

the restriction that the distribution between Southern and Northern Hemisphere needs to be as equal as possible and the previous clustering solution.

Results As can be seen in Figure 5.3, using the equitable connected clustering approach yields a significant improvement in comparison to the unmodified connected clustering. Where the unmodified connected clustering has a lowest RMSE of 22 mm, the equitable connected clustering achieves a minimum RMSE of 16 mm and generally provides similar results to choosing random but equally distributed centers. These results support the hypothesis that an equal distribution of selected cluster centers is of paramount importance when trying to capture information about the global sea level (see Hypothesis 8). Thus, this approach is a step in the right direction; however as the uniform random selection still yields comparable results we need to refine the rather rough selection of sections that were used. This brings us to the next step, in which the division of the globe into sections is improved.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of the RMSE of the mean time series of the clustered centers using equitable clustering (purple line) and the global mean sea level and the RMSE of the time series of equally distributed, but randomly chosen centers and the global mean sea level (yellow line). As the baseline the RMSE of the mean time series of all tide gauge stations (gray line), the random selection (red line), the original connected clustering (teal line) and the global mean sea level is reported (red line).

5.2 Voronoi based Equitable Connected Clustering

The creation of appropriate sections for equitable connected clustering is a non-trivial problem for two main reasons. One reason for this is that if the sections are chosen in such a simplified way as in the previous section, this can lead to fractures in the input graph. For example considering the

division between North America and South America in Figure 5.2 at 0° latitude, the sea level line graph would normally connect both and thus tide gauge stations there could be clustered together. If they are in different sections, this is not possible anymore, thus limiting the clustering algorithm. The second reason for this is that if the ratio of ocean size and the number of tide gauge stations that are present in the given section is chosen in a detrimental way, the resulting clustering solution will not be able to compensate for this. For example if the border between North America and Europe in Figure 5.2 is moved even closer to Europe, the percentage of k that is assigned to the section containing Europe is reduced. As the tide gauge stations are situated along the coastlines, determining where the border between two continents should be is a difficult task. Thus, choosing arbitrary polygons on the globe does not do justice to the idea of trying to create an equitable connected clustering. Here it would be advantageous to consider the area of the ocean that each tide gauge station represents. These two considerations can be addressed when basing the partitioning on the Voronoi diagram that is generated by the tide gauge stations.

5.2.1 Voronoi diagram

Since its first formal introduction in 1908 by Georgy Voronoy [Vor08], the Voronoi diagram has been used and discussed in a variety of scientific fields and for many applications. It is also known under the names Voronoi tessellation, Voronoi decomposition, Dirichlet tessellation (as Peter Gustav Lejeune Dirichlet worked on related concepts in 1850) and Thiessen polygons (after Alfred H. Thiessen who applied the concept to meteorology). Broadly speaking, a Voronoi diagram describes a partitioning of a given space, based on a set of features (points in that space) such that the points in each region are closer to its center than to any other center [Aur91]. According to Aurenhammer, Voronoi diagrams are useful in three main ways: “As a structure per se that makes explicit natural processes, as an auxiliary structure for investigating and calculating related mathematical objects, and as a data structure for algorithmic problems that are inherently geometric.”[Aur91]. The areas for which Voronoi diagrams have been studied are as diverse as meteorology, forestry, chemistry, archeology and biology among others [Oka+00]. Voronoi diagrams even occur naturally, for example in crystal growth or spider webs [Aur91]. Regarding geography and geosciences, there is a rich history of using Voronoi diagrams, for example for facility allocation, earthquake distribution analysis, rainfall-runoff modeling or climate system modeling [HLH14]. For definition of the Voronoi diagram based on geographical distance, we follow the notation of Hu, Liu, and Hu [HLH14]. Assuming that a set of geospatial features $G = g_1, \dots, g_n$ on the ellipsoidal earth is given, each feature is called a Voronoi generator. In the case discussed in this thesis, each

geospatial feature is a single point, defined by latitude and longitude. For two geospatial features g_i and g_j (a point on the globe) let d^G be the distance of the shortest path along the surface of the reference ellipsoid at sea level. For a given point p , define the dominance of g_i over g_j as $R(g_i|g_j) = p | d^G(p, g_i) \leq d^G(p, g_j), g_i \in G, g_j \in G, i \neq j$. Now for each $g_i \in G$ the Voronoi region $V(g_i)$ is composed by all points for which g_i is dominant over all other generators. The **Voronoi diagram** based on G is then given as $V(G) = \bigcap_{g_i \in G} V(g_i)$ [HLH14]. Because the Earth is not a plane, all map projections to a plane are unable to be accurate regarding distances on a global scale. Certain map projections can accurately capture distances for certain regions, however this is not helpful when working at a global scale. Thus, ideally the creation of the **Voronoi diagram** is performed on a sphere or ellipsoid. Methods of how to generate the **Voronoi diagram** on the ellipsoidal or spherical Earth have been explored quite a bit, mostly through either raster- or vector based approaches (see for example [AP85], [Oka+00], [Mil71], [Ren97], [HLH14]). In this thesis, the method by Caroli et al. [Car+10] is used [Vir+20]. Here the calculation of Voronoi polygons is based on a spherical model of the earth, which of course does not capture all facets and can lead to small inaccuracies. However as the **Voronoi diagram** is simply the basis for a better partitioning of the globe for the equitable connected clustering approach, these inaccuracies are not as significant. The same considerations must be applied when determining the area of a given polygon. To address this we use the calculation of geodesic polygons on an ellipsoid (see [PRO24]). With the foundational concepts of **Voronoi diagrams** established, the subsequent section discusses the methodology we build upon them.

5.2.2 Method

Calculating the **Voronoi diagram** using the tide gauge stations as generators provides an inverse density measure, as each region represents the area covered by its corresponding tide gauge station. However, this does not necessarily imply that each tide gauge station is a good representation of the entire region it covers, particularly for tide gauge stations in the Southern Hemisphere. Instead, it reflects the current situation, characterized by an unequal distribution of tide gauge stations. The method we propose uses the **Voronoi diagram** in conjunction with the **sea level line graph** to form input sections for the **equitable connected clustering** algorithm. This approach sets out to address the issues formulated in Section 5.1, namely the possibility of fracturing the input graph and introducing bias through an uneven ratio of tide gauge stations and area per section. This method works as follows.

First, the **Voronoi diagram** and the **sea level line graph** are calculated for a given time step based on the tide gauge stations that have valid data during that interval, as can be seen in **Figure 5.4a**. Next, the regions for all tide gauge stations that are part of the same connected component of the **sea level line graph** are merged (see **Figure 5.4b**). Lastly, as can be seen in **Figure 5.4c**, we filter the dry land from the area of the sections by applying a mask that hides it.

Then we continue with the **equitable connected clustering** as described in **Section 5.1**. The Algorithm that we use to calculate the **Voronoi diagram** has one downside for this specific application. While it is suitable for calculating the **Voronoi diagram** on a sphere and a mask can easily be applied afterwards, the correct approach would be to modify the algorithm so that the expansion of the polygons halts when encountering land. As it stands now, it is possible that a Voronoi region reaches across land and is thus divided into two or more pieces. If this happens, the Voronoi polygon is no longer an appropriate representation of the area that is covered by the generating tide gauge station. It is important to note that this is not a failing of the algorithm, but rather specific to the use case of this thesis. It would not be enough to include the land polygons as geospatial features into the creation of the Voronoi polygons (some algorithms can handle arbitrary geospatial features and do not require them to be simple points in space). However, this would lead to each land mass having its own region that would reach into the ocean and thus would distort the regions of the tide gauge stations. For now, the resulting inaccuracies are deemed to be acceptable, as they are not too pronounced for the considered time interval and a modification of the **Voronoi diagram** algorithm is proposed as future work. Still, it is important to keep this issue in mind, especially for

(a) Voronoi diagram based on tide gauge stations.

(b) Sections based on summed Voronoi polygons for connected components of the Sea Level Line Graph.

(c) Sections with land mask

Figure 5.4: Voronoi diagram and resulting partitioning of the globe into coherent regions based on the **sea level line graph**.

points in time when there are few tide gauge stations, as this phenomenon increases as the number shrinks.

Experiments As the proposed method is intended as an improvement of the previous approach, it is sensible that the same experiments (see Section 5.1) are performed and the results are compared to the results of the previous section.

Results The resulting RMSE between the global mean sea level and the equitable connected clustering based on the Voronoi diagram performs better than the other clustering approaches, especially when considering smaller numbers of centers. Considering Figure 5.5a, for $k \leq 400$, the clustered results based on the Voronoi diagram (blue line) perform consistently better than the other clustering approaches. However, it is interesting to see, that the simple partitioning we used in Section 5.1 (purple line) seems to yield better results for $650 \leq k \leq 450$. Interpreting the complete curve of the current approach, it is evident that using the appropriate area for each connected component of the sea level line graph leads to a much more consistent reduction of the RMSE than the other approaches and does produce better results with fewer clusters. When comparing the resulting RMSE to the RMSE between the random distribution that is equal per hemisphere and the global mean sea level, one can see that the random distribution is still a valid competitor (see Figure 5.5b). We assume that this is because the random selection enforces a balance of centers between the hemispheres and thus might be better at capturing especially the seasonal differences in sea level, as these tend to be diametrically opposed on the hemispheres. At the point where the Voronoi based clustering has

(a) Comparison between the basic connected clustering approach (teal line), equitable connected clustering (purple line) and Voronoi based equitable connected clustering (blue line).

(b) Comparison between the Voronoi based equitable connected clustering (blue line) and the random uniformly distributed selection of centers (yellow line).

Figure 5.5: Results of the Voronoi based equitable connected clustering.

Figure 5.6: Distribution of cluster centers for $k = 350$ and 150. In (a) there is an image of all tide gauge stations for comparison.

a smaller k and thus a more equal distribution of the cluster centers between the hemispheres is enforced, the results of the Voronoi based clustering are significantly better than the randomly selected tide gauge stations. This indicates that this clustering approach produces a better selection of tide gauge stations to approximate the global mean sea level, but suffers from a less equal distribution for larger k . In Figure 5.6 the distribution of cluster centers across the globe is displayed. For $k = 350$ the distribution across the hemispheres is quite equal, whereas for $k = 150$, there is even a slight bias towards the Southern Hemisphere. This makes sense as there is more ocean area in the Southern hemisphere and thus, the equitable connected clustering algorithm based on the Voronoi diagram selects more stations there.

Lastly, we would like to raise the point that there are so few tide gauge stations across the globe and they are always situated along the coastline, thus, simply taking the mean of the cluster centers to approximate the global mean sea level might not capture the whole complexity of this task. In the next chapter, we explore a more elaborate approach to reconstruct global sea levels by combining the clustered tide gauge stations and the data from satellite altimetry.

Chapter 6

Reconstructing of Global Sea Level Data

Lastly, to test our connected clustering approach, we use the tide gauge stations that are cluster centers in a reconstruction of the global sea level that utilizes satellite altimetry data in combination with tide gauge records. As global satellite altimetry sea level data is only available from 1993 onwards, the only information about historic sea level behavior that is attainable are the time series from the tide gauge stations. One of the drawbacks this includes is that the information is limited to the specific location of the tide gauge station, whereas the data from satellite altimetry exists in a comparatively fine grid. An approach to reconstruct global ocean surface temperature was introduced by Kaplan et al. [Kap+97] in 1997 by combining global modern satellite altimetry data and long-term records. In 2004 Church et al. [Chu+04] applied the same approach to global sea levels. They state that other approaches to determine global sea level rise from the few long term records that are available produce a range of results between 1 mm and $1.9 \pm 0.6 \text{ mm yr}^{-1}$ and argue this might be due to regional variances. This is in accordance with the findings from Gregory et al. [Gre+01] which present that some regions have as much as double the global sea level rise in recent history. The Arctic Ocean for example presents more than average sea level rise in most models, whereas the Southern Ocean lies consistently under the global average [Gre+01]. As the impact of a rise in sea level is drastic, investigating local as well as global sea level changes to the best of our abilities is crucial. Church et al. [Chu+04] argue that using as many tide gauge stations as possible in the reconstruction of global and regional sea levels increases the accuracy of the predictions. We investigate whether using fewer, but objectively representative and well distributed tide gauge stations might provide us with better reconstruction results than simply using all available stations, due to an elimination of the bias towards measurements from the Northern Hemisphere.

6.1 Method

We base our reconstruction of historic global sea levels mostly on the method described by Church et al. [Chu+04] and Uebbing [Ueb22]. The underlying assumption is that spatial and temporal variance patterns in sea level height that occur across the globe can be separated using **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)**. To achieve this, a data matrix H containing the time series for each grid point as rows is decomposed using singular value decomposition. For this analysis, we utilize sea level data from satellite altimetry (see [Subsection 2.1.3](#)), which has been measured in regular time intervals from 1993 until now. Singular value decomposition is a technique that decomposes a data matrix into three matrices $H = USV^T$, where U contains the left singular vectors, S is a diagonal matrix of singular values and V is comprised of the right singular values.

The columns of U are also known as **Empirical Orthogonal Functions (EOFs)** and represent the spatial patterns of the underlying data as can be seen in [Figure 6.1a](#) and [Figure 6.1c](#) where the first two EOFs are displayed. In the first EOF ([Figure 6.1a](#)) seasonal effects can be seen, where the sea level height is higher/lower for one hemisphere than for the other. The columns of SV^T , also known as **Principal Components (PCs)** contain the temporal patterns of the underlying data. The PCs contain data for each point in the time interval, whereas the EOFs contain data for every point in the grid. Recombining the two would once again produce the data matrix H with a value for every point in the time interval and every spatial point on the grid. Two examples of PCs can be found in [Figure 6.1b](#) and [Figure 6.1d](#) (blue lines). At this point the percentage of the total variance that each EOF and PC pair contains can additionally be extracted, enabling us to use a subset of them for the reconstruction. This is a simplified explanation of the PCA process; for a more detailed description see for example [JM92], [Chu+04], [Ueb22].

Under the assumption that the spatial patterns do not change substantially over time, we can use observed data from tide gauge stations to estimate the corresponding temporal amplitude for each pattern, thus replacing the PCs. This can be seen in [Figure 6.1b](#) and [Figure 6.1d](#) where the red line contains the estimated temporal amplitude. Summing the product of the spatial patterns and the estimated temporal patterns yields a complete reconstruction of global sea levels that contains data for every point on the grid and every point in time from the tide gauge data.

In our specific case, this is done as follows; first we extract the data grid from the **altimetry data set** (see [Subsection 2.1.3](#)). The data consists of a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid (around 28×28 km at the equator), containing overall 1,036,800 grid points with 366 values each (one per month). Then we

Figure 6.1: Empirical Orthogonal Functions and their corresponding Principal Components. The red line in (b) and (c) denotes the estimated principal component based on the clustered tide gauge data using Voronoi based equitable clustering with $k = 350$.

construct a data matrix H of size $p \times n$, such that each row in H represents one of the p grid points and thus contains the time series for this specific grid point and each column represents one of the n distinct points in time. As we are working with a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ grid in a Mercator projection, we have to weight our data matrix to adjust for the curvature of the earth, as 0.25° longitude is around 27 kilometers at the equator but shrinks to zero when moving to the poles. Thus, without a weight function, the data from the grid points nearing the poles would have a greater influence than the data from the equator, due to the density of the grid points. Other weighting schemes could theoretically be applied at this stage, such as emphasizing points known to contain critical information. However, we are content with correcting the area distortion by multiplying the value at each grid point with the cosine of its latitude.

The weighted data matrix H_w is then decomposed into its singular values and singular vectors $H_w = USV^T$, using singular value decomposition. We can now extract the EOFs from the columns of the eigenvector matrix U which encodes spatial patterns in the data. Each of them has p entries, where p is the number of grid points, which allows us visualization of each EOF on the grid as can be seen in Figure 6.1a and Figure 6.1c. At this point we can limit the EOFs that are being

considered, as the lower-order EOFs contain more variance than the higher order ones, which are often discarded as mostly noise in the data. Church et al. [Chu+04] propose to only use the lowest m EOFs, with $m = 10, 15, 20, 25, 30$ when reconstructing the global sea surface height. We use $m = 10$, as the explained variance drops to under 1 % after that. Now we have the first part of the equation for the reconstruction (see Equation (6.1)), which is the spatial patterns $U_m(x, y)$. Next, we need to estimate the coefficients $\alpha(t)$ by projecting the data of the previously computed cluster centers (a subset of all tide gauge stations) onto this basis.

$$H_r(x, y, t) = U_m(x, y)\alpha(t)_r \quad (6.1)$$

For this, we preprocess the PSMSL data set as follows. First, we correct the measured values for the Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA), by subtracting the vertical motion of the solid earth (mm/yr) provided by Peltier [Pel04],[Pel24]. We mean center each time series as a means to account for the differences in reference datum for each tide gauge station. This approach only works when considering a comparatively short timespan. When working with a longer timespan for reconstructing historic sea level data, one would need to consider the difference between each pair of adjacent time steps instead. For more on this process, see Church et al. [Chu+04]. Additionally, we determine the closest grid point to the geographic location of each tide gauge station and convert the sea level measurements from millimeter to meter, as this is the unit that is used in the altimetry dataset.

For each point in time we then do the following: we build a $m \times 1$ observation vector l , where m is the number of tide gauge stations used for reconstruction at this point in time (these are the precomputed cluster centers). We then calculate the linear least squares estimation $l + v = A\alpha_r$, with A being the matrix containing the EOFs for the grid points that have a tide gauge station associated to them, α_r the coefficients that need to be calculated and v containing the residuals. Lastly, inserting the coefficients α_r into Equation (6.1) results in a complete grid for each point in time.

6.2 Experiments

To investigate whether the method described above produces suitable reconstruction results, we use the clustering results from Section 5.2 for $k = 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, 550, 600, 650$ and 700 and the altimetry data set to reconstruct the global sea level between 1993

and 2023 according to the method described above. We then compare the results to the mean global sea level using the **RMSE** and evaluate how clusterings of different sizes perform in the reconstruction process. Additionally, we evaluate the reconstructed solution by comparing the time series of tide gauge stations that were not used in the reconstruction process to the reconstructed values at the closest grid point. In order to do this, the tide gauge stations are filtered to exclude the cluster centers of the current clustering (as those were used in the reconstruction). Subsequently, the ten stations with the longest time series in the time interval are selected and their time series is compared to the reconstructed time series at the closest grid point using the **RMSE**. To evaluate whether the Voronoi based **equitable connected clustering** is indeed advantageous compared to the other connected clustering approaches, we investigate how the connected clustering and the simple **equitable connected clustering** perform in the reconstruction.

6.3 Results

As examples for the resulting global sea level from the reconstruction, we provide the time series for the Voronoi based equitable connected clustering result with 100, 350 and 700 cluster centers (see [Figure 6.2a](#) [Figure 6.2b](#) and [Figure 6.2c](#)). Those three were chosen because the reconstructed values for the second one are the best if compared to the global sea level (see [Figure 6.2d](#)), whereas the first and third one performed the worst. In [Figure 6.2b](#) the reconstructed sea level (red line) is much closer to the global sea level based on altimetry data (teal line) than in [Figure 6.2c](#). As we only use the first ten **EOFs** for the reconstruction, we also plot the global sea level based on the original **EOFs** and **PCs** restricted to the first ten (yellow line) for a better comparison.

The difference in the reconstructed solution that is caused by the cluster size (see [Figure 6.2d](#)) is a first indication that the proposed clustering approach might indeed lead to an improvement in the reconstruction of global sea level, as the best reconstruction is achieved with around 350 cluster centers with a **RMSE** of 7.8 mm. The **RMSE** rises to 11.82 mm when using all tide gauge stations that have data for the time span in the reconstruction. We would like to additionally point out, that this approach achieves solutions that are closer to the mean global sea level than than taking the mean of the cluster centers (discussed in [Section 5.2](#)). However, as the satellite altimetry data is used in both the reconstruction and the evaluation, this is not necessarily surprising.

The reconstruction results when using **equitable connected clustering** and connected clustering are shown in [Figure 6.3a](#) and [Figure 6.3b](#) respectively. Neither method performs as well as the Voronoi

based approach, with the **RMSE** being at least one centimeter higher. Nevertheless, it seems clear that reducing the number of stations through clustering offers advantages over using all available tide gauge stations.

Figure 6.2: Results of the reconstruction of the global sea level using the Voronoi based equitable connected clustering.

In addition to the global results, we also evaluated the reconstruction locally by comparing the time series of tide gauge stations that were not included in the reconstruction with the reconstructed time series at the closest grid point to each of these station, as described above. In **Figure 6.4** we present the minimum, maximum and average RMSE for the different numbers of clusters (teal, yellow and red line respectively). Here the most similar time series of a tide gauge station has a **RMSE** of 4 cm and the most different one is at 40 cm, thus there is a rather high variability in the quality of the results. As discussed throughout this thesis, there are rather few tide gauge stations in comparison to the number of grid points from the altimetry data, which might be a cause of these less than optimal results. Especially considering the average RMSE (red line), it seems to be the case that using a larger number of stations leads to an

improvement of local accuracy, which is interesting as it decreases global accuracy. This result

(a) RMSE between the reconstruction based on equitable connected clustering and the global sea level.

(b) RMSE between the between the reconstruction based on connected clustering and the global sea level.

Figure 6.3: Results of the reconstruction of the global sea level using the voronoi based uniformly distributed connected clustering.

might be due to the fact that the likelihood that tide gauge stations that are close to the evaluated stations have been used in the reconstruction is increased. Geographically close tide gauge stations tend to produce similar measurements, which likely explains the increase in local accuracy.

In Figure 6.5 two exemplary time series are displayed. The first one (Figure 6.5a) from a tide gauge station in Alicante in Spain is approximated rather well by the reconstructed closest grid point (red line), whereas the second one (Figure 6.5b) from Den Helder in the Netherlands is not matched as well. An important point to keep in mind is that the stations for the comparison were chosen because they have the longest time series in the considered interval, so these are not necessarily the ones with the time series that are the most similar to the reconstructed time series. Additionally, we did not factor the distance from the tide gauge station to its closest grid point into the evaluation, but this could have an influence on the quality of the results. As this is simply a first approach to the reconstruction of global sea level based on connected clustering, there is of course room for improvement, and several of the necessary steps that are intended for the future are discussed in Section 7.1.

Figure 6.4: The minimum, maximum and average RMSE between the time series of the selected stations and the reconstructed time series at the closest grid point.

(a) Tide gauge station 960 (Alicante, Spain).

(b) Tide gauge station 23 (Den Helder, Netherlands).

Figure 6.5: Examples of the comparison between selected tide gauge stations and their closest grid point from the reconstructed sea level data. The red line is the reconstructed time series from the closest grid point, whereas the teal line is the time series of the tide gauge station.

To summarize, reconstructing the global sea level using this approach offers key advantages. First, it produces a complete grid of data, enabling the extraction of both local and global information, whereas previously, we could only approximate the global mean sea level. Although there is room for improvement in local accuracy, this method allows for detailed local analysis. Second, the approximation of the global mean sea level is significantly more accurate, as it integrates knowledge from both the altimetry data set and tide gauge records. Finally, as demonstrated in this chapter, the Voronoi-based *equitable connected clustering* method proves to be superior to the other clustering methods examined in this thesis for this specific application.

Chapter 7

Conclusion

In this thesis we set out to apply a connected clustering algorithm to a use case borrowed from the field of geodesy, specifically to gain information about global sea levels based on local tide gauge data. Tide gauge data provides the only long form record of sea level behavior, as observations through satellite altimetry are only available for the recent past (from 1993 — today). Although tide gauge data reaches further into the past than any other available source, it has notable limitations. First, the tide gauge stations are only situated along the coastlines and do not provide any information about sea level behavior at the open sea. Second, their distribution across the globe is uneven, with a concentration in the Northern Hemisphere. Consequently, using all tide gauge stations to derive information about global sea level behavior would lead to biased conclusions.

This thesis begins with a description of three distinct data sets. The first contains measurement obtained through tide gauge stations from 1807 until the present. The second is based on oceanographic models covering the period from 1958 to 2023. Observations obtained through satellite altimetry make up the third data set. While the first two are utilized in the clustering approach, the third is primarily employed for evaluation and the reconstruction of global sea levels. Following this, the thesis discusses the utilized similarity measures and evaluation criteria, along with an introduction to clustering in general and connected clustering in particular.

To assess whether connected clustering is a suitable approach for the use case at hand, we implemented the connected clustering algorithm for line graphs ([Dre+22]) and developed two different methods to calculate the input graph ^{1,2}. We show that using the [sea level line graph](#), a graph

¹Code is publicly available at <https://github.com/JohannaHillebrand/global-connected-tide-gauge-station-clustering>

²Results are publicly available at <https://bit.ly/connected-clustering-sea-level-data>

that uses the similarity of the tide gauge stations time series as well as their geographic distances, produces far better results than one that only considers geographic distances. In a next step we evaluate different approaches to improve the clustering solution, for example through a partitioning of the time series, applying mean centering and detrending. Our findings show that partitioning the time series combined with mean centering and detrending enhances the clustering result. More precisely it reduces the number of clusters for a given difference between the time series of a cluster center and the stations within its cluster.

Next we examine whether the mean of the cluster centers serves as a good approximation of the mean global sea level. Since global sea level data is only available since 1993, we focus on this time period to further investigate the connected clustering approach. Our results show that, while the connected clustering solution outperforms both the mean of all available tide gauge time series and a randomly selected solution of the same size, it is still inferior to a random solution that is equitable between the hemispheres. We attribute this phenomenon to the clustering algorithm's lack of awareness regarding the distribution of the cluster centers on the globe. The algorithm clusters stations solely based on the similarity of their time series and their connections in the input graph. Consequently, the resulting clustering might group stations together that should better be left alone, which is especially true for regions with sparse station coverage to begin with. To address this issue, we propose a new technique — [equitable connected clustering](#) – in which the globe is divided into partitions and each of these partitions is clustered separately using the connected clustering algorithm. The number of clusters assigned to each area is proportional to the oceanic area of the partition.

This partitioning of the globe is further refined by calculating the [Voronoi diagram](#), using the tide gauges stations as generators, and merging Voronoi polygons that are connected in the [sea level line graph](#). We demonstrate that this method, called Voronoi based equitable connected clustering, outperforms the other approaches in approximating the global mean sea level.

Finally, we combine the key elements of this thesis to reconstruct a global sea level grid based on the clustered tide gauge station data and satellite altimetry observations. To achieve this, we utilize a technique that separates the satellite altimetry data into its spatial and temporal patterns through singular value decomposition, as introduced by [\[Chu+04\]](#) and replace the temporal pattern with estimates derived from the cluster centers measurements. Our findings demonstrate that using the clustered solutions produces superior results in contrast to simply using all tide gauge stations in the reconstruction.

In conclusion, we establish that connected clustering of tide gauge stations is a suitable approach for this geodetic application. It reduces the number of stations without sacrificing critical information, equalizes their distribution across the globe and consistently improves the accuracy of the results.

7.1 Future Work

There are several promising directions for future research. While this thesis primarily employs the **RMSE** to emphasize the influence of extreme sea level differences on the resulting clustering, exploring alternative difference measures could offer valuable insights. For example, in certain areas and applications, introducing a technique of measurement that allows temporal flexibility — by comparing values to their most similar counterparts in the other time series within a defined time window — might prove beneficial. Additionally, investigating alternative clustering approaches could yield further insights.

Regarding the Voronoi based **equitable connected clustering**, a modification of the algorithm creating the Voronoi diagram such that it incorporated boundaries (when dry land is encountered) might improve this approach. For future work it would furthermore be interesting to investigate if removing the seasonal fluctuations from the time series would change the results seen in this thesis. Additionally investigating the radii of the clustered solutions and the uniformly distributed random solution could provide further insights regarding the solution quality.

In terms of approximating global mean sea level, combining **equitable connected clustering** with other methods offers an interesting avenue for future research. Notably, there has been significant research into using a few long-term tide gauge time series to estimate historic sea level rise (see [Dou91]). Incorporating this approach with connected clustering could help identify tide gauge stations that are exemplary for their entire region.

Conversely, another line of research contends that using a few long-term records can not accurately capture the complex reality of sea level dynamics and proposes the use of **PCA** to base the reconstruction of global mean sea level on a combination of satellite altimetry observations and tide gauge data [Chu+04]. While we applied **equitable connected clustering** to this approach, many unexplored possibilities remain. A key area for future work would be implementing a reconstruction that extends further into the past. This would require incorporating the differences in sea levels between tide gauge stations into the reconstruction (see [Chu+04] for details). Comparing

different clustering techniques and using various comparison metrics would also provide valuable contributions. Moreover, comparing these approaches with other reconstruction methods should be explored. Finally, exploring the impact of using varying numbers of empirical orthogonal functions (EOFs) could enhance reconstruction results, as the selected number of EOFs may not fully capture the variance in the data.

Appendix

1 RECOMMENDATIONS TO AUTHORITIES CONTRIBUTING DATA TO THE PSMSL [[Per24a](#)]

General The Permanent Service appreciates the contributions from all organisations supplying mean sea level data and does not seek to impose unnecessary conditions upon contributors. Nevertheless, a minimum of quality control must be exercised if the data bank is to be an authoritative reference. To this end the PSMSL requests the following information together with each set of monthly and annual mean sea level values supplied:

- the units used (metres, rarely feet),
- a statement of the datum to which the values refer,
- a statement of the measured depth of that datum below the primary tide gauge bench mark (TGBM),
- an indication of incomplete or deduced data (see paragraph b),
- the number of observations per day used to calculate the monthly means,
- any information of changes in datums, bench marks or relevant procedures since the previous batch of data,
- any information on the availability of more frequent readings (e.g. hourly heights).

Although data will be accepted in any format, mean heights should preferably be in the metric system to the nearest millimetre, and the datum to which the means refer should preferably be the

tide gauge zero. Data will be gratefully received in any form (e.g. as paper tabulations in letters or via email).

Treatment of incomplete records One of the most important things for users of the mean sea level data bank to know is the accuracy of the published figures. Details of the treatment of gaps in the tidal record are of particular interest. Therefore, the PSMSL makes the following recommendations:

- small gaps in observed tidal records should be interpolated, if possible before computing monthly and annual means,
- the interpolation should be performed at an early stage in the processing. One principle to adopt is that of a comparison with the complete records from a nearby station. However we would stress that predicted values are not suitable for interpolation because of meteorological effects,
- in cases where interpolation is impossible the monthly mean should be compiled from the incomplete data. Where more than 15 days are missing from a month a mean value should not be computed,
- when sending mean values to the PSMSL, authorities are requested to indicate if interpolation has been effected or the exact number of missing days of data. These details should be sent as suffixes after each monthly mean and shown in brackets:

e.g. 2487(9) would mean 9 daily mean values were missing and not interpolated when computing the mean of 2487mm; 913(XX) would mean missing data were interpolated to provide the average of 913mm,

- if there are 11 or 12 monthly mean values available then an annual mean should be calculated. If the annual mean is computed by averaging the monthly means, the monthly means must first be weighted. The weight for each month should be the number of days for which readings were available.

Computation of monthly and annual mean values The attention of data contributors is drawn to three IOC publications entitled 'Manual on Sea Level Measurement and Interpretation' which can be

downloaded from http://www.psmsl.org/train_and_info/training/manuals/
The third one is especially worth considering with regard to monthly mean computation. The PSMSL will be pleased to assist with advice on methods of data processing and the determination of mean values.

Preservation of original data Contributors are urged to preserve the original sea level data in permanent form. The information contained in such basic time series is of great value in many scientific studies, is irreplaceable, and should not be lost to posterity. Where original data are available in computer compatible form, the PSMSL would be grateful to receive copies (and in the case of GLOSS stations, it is a requirement that any such data are provided to GLOSS Archiving Centres, of which the PSMSL is one, see below). Such global databanking of higher frequency information will evolve considerably over the next few years as a result of GLOSS and related activities.

2 Enforcing a time series overlap and the mean sea level

As can be seen in Figure 7.1 enforcing an overlap between the time series of tide gauge stations does not in general increase the resulting comparability with the mean sea level, however different approaches need to be tested in order to answer this question definitively.

Figure 7.1: Comparing the RMSE between the global mean sea level and the mean of the clustering solution with overlap constraint and the RMSE between the global mean sea level and the mean time series of all tide gauge stations

Glossary

altimetry data set Data grid containing *sea level anomaly* values between 1993 and the present. See [Subsection 2.1.3](#) for more information. 16, 38, 41, 42, 50, 52

EOF Empirical Orthogonal Function, spatial patterns of sea level height, extracted by singular value decomposition (see [Section 6.1](#)). 50–53, 60

equitable connected clustering A new clustering approach that takes the global distribution of cluster centers based on the ocean area into account (see [Section 5.1](#)). 42, 43, 45–47, 53, 55, 56, 58, 59

GIA Describes the movement of land due to glacial changes (see [[Pel24](#)]). 52

linear least squares estimation calculates the coefficients by minimising the sum of the squared errors. 52

MAE Mean Absolute Error, measure of difference between two time series based on the sum of the absolute differences (see [Equation \(2.2\)](#)).. 13

mesoscale processes Ocean signals with space scales of 50-500 km and time scales of 10-100 days [[CNE](#)]. 11

MSL Mean Sea Level, arithmetic mean of hourly sea level measurements (see [Subsection 2.1.1](#)). 4, 8, 9

MTL Mean Tide Level, arithmetic mean of mean high water and mean low water (see [Subsection 2.1.1](#)). 4, 8, 9

- ORAS5** Ocean Reanalysis System 5, combination of model data with observations across the world into a complete dataset from 1958 until the present. 7, 25, 34
- ORAS5 data set** Ocean reanalysis data set (see Subsection 2.1.2). 10, 11, 14, 26–28, 35
- PC** Principal Component, containing the temporal pattern (see Section 6.1). 50, 53
- PCA** Principal Component Analysis, linear dimensionality reduction technique (see [JM92]). 3, 50, 59
- PSMSL** Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, collecting, publishing and interpreting sea level data from global tide gauge stations (see Subsection 2.1.1). 1, 7, 9–11, 34
- PSMSL data set** Tide Gauge measurement data compiled by the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, see Subsection 2.1.1 for more information.. 7, 12–14, 25–30, 34, 35, 38, 52
- RLR** Revised Local Reference, sea level measurements reduced to a common datum (see Subsection 2.1.1). 9
- RMSE** Root Mean Squared Error, measure of difference between two sets of values by calculating the root of the squared differences (see Equation (2.1)). 13, 27, 28, 30, 39, 42, 43, 47, 53, 54, 59
- sea level anomaly** Waterheight in reference to the mean sea surface. 11, 12, 38, 64
- sea level line graph** Line graph combining geographical information and the difference between time series of tide gauge stations (see Section 4.1). 22, 24, 25, 30, 41, 44–47, 57, 58
- Voronoi diagram** The Voronoi diagram is a partition of a given space based on a set of input points, called generators (see Subsection 5.2.1). 44–48, 58

Bibliography

- [AP85] Augenbaum, Jeffrey M and Peskin, Charles S. “On the construction of the Voronoi mesh on a sphere”. In: *Journal of Computational Physics* 59.2 (1985). DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991\(85\)90140-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0021-9991(85)90140-8).
- [Aur91] Aurenhammer, Franz. “Voronoi diagrams—a survey of a fundamental geometric data structure”. In: *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 23.3 (1991). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/116873.116880>.
- [Bar+16] Barbosa, SM et al. “Wavelet-based clustering of sea level records”. In: *Mathematical Geosciences* 48 (2016). DOI: [10.1007/s11004-015-9623-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11004-015-9623-9).
- [Car+10] Caroli, Manuel et al. “Robust and Efficient Delaunay Triangulations of Points on Or Close to a Sphere”. In: *Experimental Algorithms*. 2010. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-13193-6_39.
- [Chu+04] Church, John A et al. “Estimates of the regional distribution of sea level rise over the 1950–2000 period”. In: *Journal of climate* 17.13 (2004). DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(2004\)017<2609:EOTRDO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(2004)017<2609:EOTRDO>2.0.CO;2).
- [CNE] CNES, (Centre National d’Etudes Spatiales). *What are mesoscale processes? A brief description of mesoscale processes observed by altimetry*. URL: <https://www.aviso.altimetry.fr/en/applications/ocean/mesoscale-circulation/mesoscale-processes-at-the-ctoh/what-are-mesoscale-processes.html#:~:text=The%20mesoscale%20variability%20generally%20refers,have%20a%20lower%20sea%20level>. (visited on 08/27/2024).
- [Cop18] Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), Climate Data Store (CDS). *Sea level gridded data from satellite observations for the global ocean from 1993 to present*. 2018. DOI: [10.24381/cds.4c328c78](https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.4c328c78). (Visited on 07/15/2024).
- [Cop21] Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). *ORAS5 global ocean reanalysis monthly data from 1958 to present*. 2021. DOI: [10.24381/cds.67e8eeb7](https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.67e8eeb7). (Visited on 04/16/2024).

- [Dou91] Douglas, Bruce C. “Global sea level rise”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 96.C4 (1991). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/91JC00064>.
- [Dre+22] Drexler, Lukas et al. “Connected k-Center and k-Diameter Clustering”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:2211.02176* (2022). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2211.02176>.
- [Eve11] Everitt, Brian. *Cluster analysis*. 5th ed. Wiley series in probability and statistics. 2011. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00154794>.
- [Ge+08] Ge, Rong et al. “Joint cluster analysis of attribute data and relationship data: The connected k-center problem, algorithms and applications”. In: *ACM Trans. Knowl. Discov. Data* 2.2 (2008). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/1376815.1376816>.
- [GPS11] Gupta, Neelima, Pancholi, Aditya, and Sabharwal, Yogish. “Clustering with internal connectedness”. In: *International Workshop on Algorithms and Computation*. 2011. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-19094-0_17.
- [Gre+01] Gregory, James Monroe et al. “Comparison of results from several AOGCMs for global and regional sea-level change 1900–2100”. In: *Climate Dynamics* 18 (2001). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s003820100180>.
- [HLH14] Hu, Hai, Liu, XiaoHang, and Hu, Peng. “Voronoi diagram generation on the ellipsoidal earth”. In: *Computers & Geosciences* 73 (2014). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2014.08.011>.
- [Hoc84] Hochbaum, Dorit S. “When are NP-hard location problems easy?” In: *Annals of Operations Research* (1984). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01874389>.
- [Hof17] Hofer, Matthias. “Mean centering”. In: *The international encyclopedia of communication research methods* (2017). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118901731.iecrm0137>.
- [Hol+13] Holgate, Simon J. et al. “New Data Systems and Products at the Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level”. In: *Journal of Coastal Research: Volume 29, Issue 3: pp. 493 – 504* (2013). DOI: [10.2112/JCOASTRES-D-12-00175.1](https://doi.org/10.2112/JCOASTRES-D-12-00175.1).
- [Jet24] Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, NASA. *Why Study the Ocean*. 2024. URL: <https://sealevel.jpl.nasa.gov/ocean-observation/why-study-the-ocean/overview/> (visited on 04/12/2024).
- [JM92] Joliffe, Ian T and Morgan, BJT. “Principal component analysis and exploratory factor analysis”. In: *Statistical methods in medical research* 1.1 (1992). DOI: [10.1177/096228029200100105](https://doi.org/10.1177/096228029200100105).

Bibliography

- [Kap+97] Kaplan, Alexey et al. “Reduced space optimal analysis for historical data sets: 136 years of Atlantic sea surface temperatures”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 102.C13 (1997). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/97JC01734>.
- [LP12] Liao, Zhung-Xun and Peng, Wen-Chih. “Clustering spatial data with a geographic constraint: exploring local search”. In: *Knowledge and information systems* 31 (2012). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-011-0402-8>.
- [Mil71] Miles, RE. “Random points, sets and tessellations on the surface of a sphere”. In: *Sankhyā: The Indian Journal of Statistics, Series A* (1971).
- [Nat24] National Ocean and Atmospheric Administration. *What is a tide gauge?* 2024. URL: <https://oceanservice.noaa.gov/facts/tide-gauge.html#:~:text=While%20older%20tide%2Dmeasuring%20stations,back%20from%20the%20water's%20surface..>
- [Oka+00] Okabe, Atsuyuki et al. “Concepts and applications of Voronoi diagrams”. In: *John Wiley, Chichester* (2000). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470317013>.
- [Pel04] Peltier, W Richard. “Global glacial isostasy and the surface of the ice-age Earth: the ICE-5G (VM2) model and GRACE”. In: *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Science* 32.1 (2004). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.earth.32.082503.144359>.
- [Pel24] Peltier, W Richard. *Predictions of the rate of PSL rise due to GIA effect at PSMSL location*. 2024. URL: <https://www.atmosph.physics.utoronto.ca/~peltier/data.php> (visited on 08/26/2024).
- [Per24a] Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL). *Further Information*. 2024. URL: <https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/psmsl.hel> (visited on 04/16/2024).
- [Per24b] Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL). *Individual Station Data and Plot Notes*. 2024. URL: <https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/notes.php> (visited on 04/16/2024).
- [Per24c] Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL). *Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level - Overview*. 2024. URL: https://psmsl.org/about_us/overview/ (visited on 04/12/2024).
- [Per24d] Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL). *Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level (PSMSL)*. 2024. URL: <http://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/> (visited on 03/20/2024).
- [PRO24] PROJ contributors. *PROJ coordinate transformation software library*. Open Source Geospatial Foundation. 2024. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5884394](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5884394). URL: <https://proj.org/>.

Bibliography

- [PVK] Patterson, Tom and Vaughn Kelso, Nathaniel. *Natural Earth Physical Vectors*. URL: <https://www.natureearthdata.com/downloads/10m-physical-vectors/> (visited on 03/11/2024).
- [Ras+19] Rashid, Md Mamunur et al. “An extreme sea level indicator for the contiguous United States coastline”. In: *Scientific Data* 6.1 (2019). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-019-0333-x>.
- [Ren97] Renka, Robert J. “Algorithm 772: STRIPACK: Delaunay triangulation and Voronoi diagram on the surface of a sphere”. In: *ACM Transactions on Mathematical Software (TOMS)* 23.3 (1997). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1145/275323.275329>.
- [Rum12] Rummukainen, Markku. “Changes in climate and weather extremes in the 21st century”. In: *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 3.2 (2012). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.160>.
- [RW20] Rashid, MM and Wahl, T. “Predictability of extreme sea level variations along the US coastline”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 125.9 (2020). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020JC016295>.
- [SAB10] Scotto, Manuel G, Alonso, Andrés M, and Barbosa, Susana M. “Clustering time series of sea levels: extreme value approach”. In: *Journal of waterway, port, coastal, and ocean engineering* 136.4 (2010). DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)WW.1943-5460.0000004](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)WW.1943-5460.0000004).
- [Shc+13] Shcherbakov, Maxim Vladimirovich et al. “A survey of forecast error measures”. In: *World applied sciences journal* 24.24 (2013). DOI: [10.5829/idosi.wasj.2013.24.itmies.80032](https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.wasj.2013.24.itmies.80032).
- [SPH24] Sánchez, Laura, Pearlmén, Michael, and Heki Kosuke, Global Geodetic Observing System (GGOS). *Satellite Altimetry*. 2024. URL: <https://ggos.org/item/satellite-altimetry/> (visited on 09/09/2024).
- [Ueb22] Uebbing, Bernd. “Consistently closing global and regional sea level budgets”. PhD Thesis. Universitäts-und Landesbibliothek Bonn, 2022.
- [Uni24] University of Chicago. *Tide Gauge Sea Level*. 2024. URL: <https://sealevel.colorado.edu/tide-gauge-sea-level> (visited on 08/13/2024).
- [Vaz97] Vazirani, Vijay V. “Approximation algorithms”. In: *Georgia Inst. Tech* (1997). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-04565-7>.
- [Vir+20] Virtanen, Pauli et al. “SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python”. In: *Nature Methods* 17 (2020). DOI: [10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2).

Bibliography

- [Vor08] Voronoi, Georges. “Nouvelles applications des parametres continus a la theorie des formes quadratiques (new applications of continuous parameters to the theory of quadratic forms)”. In: *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik* 134 (1908). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/crll.1908.133.97>.
- [Woo17] Woodworth, Philip L. “Differences between mean tide level and mean sea level”. In: *Journal of Geodesy* 91.1 (2017). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00190-016-0938-1>.